

Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Orders - I

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Abstract

We know that we can always write **block-wise magic squares** of any order except for the orders of type p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. On the other hand we can always write **bordered magic squares** of any order. The aims of this work is to combine **bordered** and **block-wise** magic squares, for the magic squares of **prime** and **double prime numbers** orders. We call it as **block-bordered** magic squares. The magic squares considered in this work are of orders 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 19, 22, 23, 26, 29 and 31. In order to bring these **block-bordered** magic squares, we make use of author's previous works on **block-wise** constructions of magics squares, such as, of orders, 8, 9, 12, 16, 18, 20, 21, 24, 25 and 27. The second part of this work is for the **block-bordered** magic squares of orders 34, 37 and 38 [53]. The third part is for the magic squares of orders 41, 43, 46 and 47.

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1 Basic Magic Squares

Below are some magic squares well known in the literature. These are of orders, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7. In some cases, these magic squares are **pandiagonal**, such as of orders 4, 5 and 7. These are generally used in construction of **block-wise magic squares** given in Section 3 as Appendix or Appendix 3.

1.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 1.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 3 is given by*

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $3k$, $k > 2$.

1.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Example 1.2. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 4.*

		34	34	34	34
	7	12	1	14	34
34	2	13	8	11	34
34	16	3	10	5	34
34	9	6	15	4	34
	34	34	34	34	34

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $4k$, $k > 1$

1.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 1.3. Let's consider a *pan magic square* of order 5 is given by

		65	65	65	65	65
	1	9	12	20	23	65
65	17	25	3	6	14	65
65	8	11	19	22	5	65
65	24	2	10	13	16	65
65	15	18	21	4	7	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $5k$, $k > 2$

1.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 1.4. Let's consider a *magic square* of order 6.

						111
1	35	34	33	2	6	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $6k$, $k > 1$

1.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 1.5. Let's consider a *pan magic square* of order 7 is given by

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175	
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175	
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175	
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175	
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175	
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175	
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175	
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $7k$, $k > 2$

1.6 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 8

Example 1.6. Let's consider a *pan magic square* of order 8 is given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	25	48	1	56	26	47	2	55	260
260	8	49	32	41	7	50	31	42	260
260	64	9	40	17	63	10	39	18	260
260	33	24	57	16	34	23	58	15	260
260	27	46	3	54	28	45	4	53	260
260	6	51	30	43	5	52	29	44	260
260	62	11	38	19	61	12	37	20	260
260	35	22	59	14	36	21	60	13	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $8k$, $k > 1$

Example 1.7. Let's consider a *pandiagonal bimagic square* of order 8 given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	16	41	36	5	27	62	55	18	260
260	26	63	54	19	13	44	33	8	260
260	1	40	45	12	22	51	58	31	260
260	23	50	59	30	4	37	48	9	260
260	38	3	10	47	49	24	29	60	260
260	52	21	32	57	39	2	11	46	260
260	43	14	7	34	64	25	20	53	260
260	61	28	17	56	42	15	6	35	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

In this case, each 2×4 blocks entries sum is same as of magic square, i.e., 260.

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of bimagic squares of orders 24, 32, etc. In case of order 24 the magic square is semi-bimagic.

1.7 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 9

Example 1.8. Let's consider a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 9 is given by

		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	
	8	49	66	61	24	38	36	77	10	369
369	37	63	23	12	35	76	65	7	51	369
369	78	11	34	50	64	9	22	39	62	369
369	14	28	81	67	3	53	42	56	25	369
369	52	69	2	27	41	55	80	13	30	369
369	57	26	40	29	79	15	1	54	68	369
369	20	43	60	73	18	32	48	71	4	369
369	31	75	17	6	47	70	59	19	45	369
369	72	5	46	44	58	21	16	33	74	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Additionally it has property that each 3×3 block is of same sum as of magic square, i.e., $S_9 = 369$. Also each 3×3 block is a semi-magic square of order 3 (only in rows and columns).

Example 1.9. Let's consider a *bimagic* square of order 9 given by

									369
1	18	23	35	40	48	60	65	79	369
33	38	52	55	72	77	8	13	21	369
62	67	75	6	11	25	28	45	50	369
27	5	10	49	30	44	74	61	69	369
47	34	42	81	59	64	22	3	17	369
76	57	71	20	7	15	54	32	37	369
14	19	9	39	53	31	70	78	56	369
43	51	29	68	73	63	12	26	4	369
66	80	58	16	24	2	41	46	36	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Sums of the entries of blocks of order 9 are of equal sums as of magic square, i.e., 369. The **bimagic** sum is $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 20049$.

The **bimagic squares** of orders 8 and 9 given in examples 1.7 and 1.9 are the classical ones constructed in 1891 by G. Pfeffermann [8]. Detailed study can be seen in a work by Derkson, Eggrmont and Essen [6].

In the next section, we worked with **block-bordered** magic squares. These **block-bordered** magic squares are based on **bordered** magic squares. These **bordered** magic squares are constructed by using online program by H. White [9, 10]. In future, we shall write a simplified way to calculate bordered magic squares.

2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares

In this section, we shall write magic squares order type p or $2p$, where p is a prime number $p \geq 5$. These are written as combinations of **bordered** and **block-wise** magic squares. The magic square considered are of orders 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 19, 22, 23, 26, 29 and 31. We observe that the magic squares of orders 11, 13, 17, 19, 23 and 29 are prime orders. The magic squares of orders 10, 14, 22 and 26 are of double prime orders. The idea of considering these magic squares is that we can't construct them as **block-wise**. All of these can be constructed as **bordered magic squares** [9, 10]. This work brings mixture of **block-wise** and **bordered** magic squares, calling **block-bordered magic squares**.

2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Example 2.1. Let's consider a **bordered magic square** of order 10 given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	26	20	80	82	69	31	71	25	88
89	23	64	62	35	68	36	38	78	12
11	24	34	56	43	46	57	67	77	90
96	29	40	49	54	51	48	61	72	5
1	79	42	53	50	47	52	59	22	100
93	74	60	44	55	58	45	41	27	8
7	73	63	39	66	33	65	37	28	94
95	76	81	21	19	32	70	30	75	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic square sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{43, 44, \dots, 57, 58\}; & S_{4 \times 4} &:= 202 \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{33, 34, \dots, 41, 42, D_{4 \times 4}, 59, 60, \dots, 67, 68\}; & S_{6 \times 6} &:= 303 \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{19, 20, \dots, 31, 32, D_{6 \times 6}, 69, 70, \dots, 81, 82\}; & S_{8 \times 8} &:= 404 \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 17, 18, D_{8 \times 8}, 83, 84, \dots, 99, 100\}; & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 505.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 10

2.1.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 64 by 19 to 82 in Examples 1.6 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{8 \times 8}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 10, where magic square of order 8 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 505, \quad S_{8 \times 8} := 404 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 101.$$

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 4 with **equal magic sums**.

2.1.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 64 by 19 to 82 in Examples 1.7 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{8 \times 8}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	34	59	54	23	45	80	73	36	88
89	44	81	72	37	31	62	51	26	12
11	19	58	63	30	40	69	76	49	90
96	41	68	77	48	22	55	66	27	5
1	56	21	28	65	67	42	47	78	100
93	70	39	50	75	57	20	29	64	8
7	61	32	25	52	82	43	38	71	94
95	79	46	35	74	60	33	24	53	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 10, where magic square of order 8 is a **bimagic square** with following sums:

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 505 \quad S_{8 \times 8} := 404 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{b_{8 \times 8}} := 23132$$

The magic square of order 8 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic square**, where the blocks of order 2×8 are of same sum as of **magic square**, i.e. 404.

Summarizing, we have following result:

Result 2.1. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 in two different ways, where the **block-wise magic squares** considered are as given below:*

- (i) ***Pandiagonal magic square** of 8, where each block of order 4 is a **pandiagonal magic square** with equal magic sums;*
- (ii) ***Pandiagonal bimagic magic square** of 8, where each block of order 2×8 is of same sum as of **magic square**.*

2.2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

Example 2.2. Let's consider a *bordered magic square* of order 11 given by

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1
119	21	44	48	46	81	82	84	42	101	3
117	23	85	52	49	69	67	68	37	99	5
115	25	83	72	62	57	64	50	39	97	7
11	93	43	71	63	61	59	51	79	29	111
13	91	45	56	58	65	60	66	77	31	109
15	89	47	54	73	53	55	70	75	33	107
17	87	80	74	76	41	40	38	78	35	105
19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{57, 58, \dots, 64, 65\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 183 \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{49, 50, \dots, 55, 56, D_{3 \times 3}, 66, 67, \dots, 72, 73\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 305 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{37, 38, \dots, 47, 48, D_{5 \times 5}, 74, 75, \dots, 84, 85\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 427 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{21, 22, \dots, 35, 36, D_{7 \times 7}, 86, 87, \dots, 100, 101\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 549 \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 19, 20, D_{9 \times 9}, 102, 103, \dots, 121, 121\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 671.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 11

2.2.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 81 by 21 to 101 in Example 1.8 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{9 \times 9}$ appearing in Example 2.2, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 given by

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	42	91	50	47	84	52	40	89	54	1
119	55	41	87	48	43	92	53	45	85	3
117	86	51	46	88	56	39	90	49	44	5
115	60	28	95	65	21	97	58	26	99	7
11	100	59	24	93	61	29	98	63	22	111
13	23	96	64	25	101	57	27	94	62	109
15	78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	107
17	37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	105
19	68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 11, where magic square of order 9 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 671 \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 549 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 183$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.2.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 81 by 21 to 101 in Example 1.9 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{9 \times 9}$ appearing in Example 2.2, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 given by

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10
121	29	91	72	95	49	30	62	43	78	1
119	98	52	33	65	46	81	23	85	66	3
117	59	40	75	26	88	69	101	55	36	5
115	73	27	92	31	93	50	79	60	44	7
11	34	96	53	82	63	47	67	21	86	111
13	76	57	41	70	24	89	37	99	56	109
15	90	74	28	48	32	94	42	80	61	107
17	51	35	97	45	83	64	84	68	22	105
19	39	77	58	87	71	25	54	38	100	103
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 11, where magic square of order 9 is **bimagic square** with following sums:

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 671 \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 549 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{b_{9 \times 9}} := 38409$$

The 9 members of each block of order 3×3 are of equal sums as of magic square, i.e., 549.

Summarizing, we have following result:

Result 2.2. We have written a **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 in two different ways, where the **block-wise magic squares** considered are as given below:

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 9, where each block of order 3 is a semi-magic square with equal semi-magic sums;*
- (ii) *Bimagic magic square of 9, where sum of each block of order 3×3 are of same sum as of magic square.*

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 13

2.3 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 13

Example 2.3. Let's consider a **bordered magic square** of order 13 given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	166
6	143	45	68	72	70	105	106	108	66	125	27	164
8	141	47	109	76	73	93	91	92	61	123	29	162
10	139	49	107	96	86	81	88	74	63	121	31	160
11	35	117	67	95	87	85	83	75	103	53	135	159
154	37	115	69	80	82	89	84	90	101	55	133	16
152	39	113	71	78	97	77	79	94	99	57	131	18
150	41	111	104	98	100	65	64	62	102	59	129	20
148	43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{81, 82, \dots, 88, 89\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 255 \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{73, 74, \dots, 79, 80, D_{3 \times 3}, 90, 91, \dots, 96, 97\} & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 425 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{61, 62, \dots, 71, 72, D_{5 \times 5}, 98, 99, \dots, 108, 109\} & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 595 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{45, 46, \dots, 59, 60, D_{7 \times 7}, 110, 111, \dots, 124, 125\} & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 765 \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{25, 26, \dots, 43, 44, D_{9 \times 9}, 126, 127, \dots, 144, 145\} & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 935 \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 23, 24, D_{11 \times 11}, 146, 147, \dots, 168, 169\} & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 1105.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 13.

2.3.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 81 by 45 to 125 in Example 1.8 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{9 \times 9}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	66	115	74	71	108	76	64	113	78	25	166
6	143	79	65	111	72	67	116	77	69	109	27	164
8	141	110	75	70	112	80	63	114	73	68	29	162
10	139	84	52	119	89	45	121	82	50	123	31	160
11	35	124	83	48	117	85	53	122	87	46	135	159
154	37	47	120	88	49	125	81	51	118	86	133	16
152	39	102	97	56	107	90	58	100	95	60	131	18
150	41	61	101	93	54	103	98	59	105	91	129	20
148	43	92	57	106	94	62	99	96	55	104	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 13, where the magic square of order 9 is **pan-diagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1105, \quad D_{11 \times 11} := 935, \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 765 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 255$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** of order 3 with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.3.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 81 by 45 to 125 in Example 1.9 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{9 \times 9}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168
4	145	53	115	96	119	73	54	86	67	102	25	166
6	143	122	76	57	89	70	105	47	109	90	27	164
8	141	83	64	99	50	112	93	125	79	60	29	162
10	139	97	51	116	55	117	74	103	84	68	31	160
11	35	58	120	77	106	87	71	91	45	110	135	159
154	37	100	81	65	94	48	113	61	123	80	133	16
152	39	114	98	52	72	56	118	66	104	85	131	18
150	41	75	59	121	69	107	88	108	92	46	129	20
148	43	63	101	82	111	95	49	78	62	124	127	22
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 13, where the magic square of order 9 is **bimagic square** with following sums:

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1105, \quad D_{11 \times 11} := 935 \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 765 \text{ and } Sb_{9 \times 9} := 38409.$$

The 9 members of each block of order 3×3 are of equal sums as of magic square, i.e., 765.

Summarizing, we have following result:

Result 2.3. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 in two different ways. The **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 9, where each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square** with equal semi-magic sums;*
- (ii) *Bimagic magic square of 9, where sum of each block of order 3×3 are of same sum as of magic square.*

The process applied here is the same as in case of magic square of order 11, but with different entries.

2.4 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 14

Example 2.4. Let's consider a *bordered magic square* of order 14 given by

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184
195	160	169	29	167	31	27	48	150	46	152	44	159	2
3	42	139	134	64	132	66	62	52	146	50	140	155	194
193	41	61	74	68	128	130	117	79	119	73	136	156	4
5	157	137	71	112	110	83	116	84	86	126	60	40	192
191	158	59	72	82	104	91	94	105	115	125	138	39	6
177	165	144	77	88	97	102	99	96	109	120	53	32	20
171	154	49	127	90	101	98	95	100	107	70	148	43	26
25	36	141	122	108	92	103	106	93	89	75	56	161	172
173	35	55	121	111	87	114	81	113	85	76	142	162	24
23	163	143	124	129	69	67	80	118	78	123	54	34	174
175	33	57	63	133	65	131	135	145	51	147	58	164	22
21	38	28	168	30	166	170	149	47	151	45	153	37	176
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{91, 92, \dots, 105, 106\}; & S_{4 \times 4} &:= 394 \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{81, 82, \dots, 89, 90, D_{4 \times 4}, 107, 108, \dots, 115, 116\}; & S_{6 \times 6} &:= 591 \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{67, 68, \dots, 79, 80, D_{6 \times 6}, 117, 118, \dots, 129, 130\}; & S_{8 \times 8} &:= 788 \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{49, 50, \dots, 65, 66, D_{8 \times 8}, 131, 132, \dots, 147, 148\}; & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 985 \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{27, 28, \dots, 47, 48, D_{10 \times 10}, 149, 150, \dots, 169, 170\}; & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 1182 \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 25, 26, D_{12 \times 12}, 171, 172, \dots, 195, 196\}; & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 1379.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are three different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 14.

2.4.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 144 by 27 to 170 in Example 3.1 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{12 \times 12}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 given by

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184
195	124	27	77	98	48	145	104	54	151	166	69	119	2
3	29	76	123	144	97	50	150	103	56	71	118	165	194
193	75	125	28	49	146	96	55	152	102	117	167	70	4
5	157	60	110	113	63	160	83	33	130	139	42	92	192
191	62	109	156	159	112	65	129	82	35	44	91	138	6
177	108	158	61	64	161	111	34	131	81	90	140	43	20
171	93	143	46	31	128	78	73	170	120	99	149	52	26
25	47	94	141	126	79	32	168	121	74	53	100	147	172
173	142	45	95	80	30	127	122	72	169	148	51	101	24
23	114	164	67	58	155	105	40	137	87	84	134	37	174
175	68	115	162	153	106	59	135	88	41	38	85	132	22
21	163	66	116	107	57	154	89	39	136	133	36	86	176
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14, where the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1379 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{12 \times 12} := 1182.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **magic squares** of order 3 with **different magic sums**.

2.4.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 144 by 27 to 170 in Example 3.3 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{12 \times 12}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 given by

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184
195	81	134	27	152	82	133	28	151	83	132	29	150	2
3	44	135	98	117	43	136	97	118	42	137	96	119	194
193	170	45	116	63	169	46	115	64	168	47	114	65	4
5	99	80	153	62	100	79	154	61	101	78	155	60	192
191	84	131	30	149	85	130	31	148	86	129	32	147	6
177	41	138	95	120	40	139	94	121	39	140	93	122	20
171	167	48	113	66	166	49	112	67	165	50	111	68	26
25	102	77	156	59	103	76	157	58	104	75	158	57	172
173	87	128	33	146	88	127	34	145	89	126	35	144	24
23	38	141	92	123	37	142	91	124	36	143	90	125	174
175	164	51	110	69	163	52	109	70	162	53	108	71	22
21	105	74	159	56	106	73	160	55	107	72	161	54	176
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14, where magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1379, \quad S_{12 \times 12} := 1182 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 394.$$

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 4 with **equal magic sums**.

2.4.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 144 by 27 to 170 in Example 3.4 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{12 \times 12}$ appearing in Example 2.4, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 given by

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184
195	27	163	162	155	34	50	28	164	161	156	33	49	2
3	146	58	138	59	67	123	145	57	137	60	68	124	194
193	122	115	83	90	106	75	121	116	84	89	105	76	4
5	98	82	107	114	91	99	97	81	108	113	92	100	192
191	51	130	66	131	139	74	52	129	65	132	140	73	6
177	147	43	35	42	154	170	148	44	36	41	153	169	20
171	29	165	160	157	32	48	30	166	159	158	31	47	26
25	144	56	136	61	69	125	143	55	135	62	70	126	172
173	120	117	85	88	104	77	119	118	86	87	103	78	24
23	96	80	109	112	93	101	95	79	110	111	94	102	174
175	53	128	64	133	141	72	54	127	63	134	142	71	22
21	149	45	37	40	152	168	150	46	38	39	151	167	176
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 with following sums:

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1379, \quad S_{12 \times 12} := 1182 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 591.$$

Blocks of order 6 are **magic square** of order 6 with **equal magic sums**.

Summarizing, we have following result:

Result 2.4. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 in three different ways. The **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 12, where each block of order 3 is a magic square with different magic sums;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 12, where each block of order 4 is a pandiagonal magic square with equal magic sums;*
- (iii) *Magic square of order 12, where each block of order 6 is a magic square with equal magic sums.*

2.5 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 17

Example 2.5. *Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 17 given by*

16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18
1	242	231	233	235	237	239	241	243	43	41	39	37	35	33	46	289
3	34	216	207	209	211	213	215	217	69	67	65	63	61	72	256	287
5	36	62	96	104	102	100	98	197	198	200	202	204	94	228	254	285
7	38	64	205	112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	85	226	252	283
9	40	66	203	105	128	132	130	165	166	168	126	185	87	224	250	281
11	42	68	201	107	169	136	133	153	151	152	121	183	89	222	248	279
13	44	70	199	109	167	156	146	141	148	134	123	181	91	220	246	277
273	45	71	95	177	127	155	147	145	143	135	163	113	195	219	245	17
271	240	214	97	175	129	140	142	149	144	150	161	115	193	76	50	19
269	238	212	99	173	131	138	157	137	139	154	159	117	191	78	52	21
267	236	210	101	171	164	158	160	125	124	122	162	119	189	80	54	23
265	234	208	103	176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	187	82	56	25
263	232	206	196	186	188	190	192	93	92	90	88	86	194	84	58	27
261	230	218	83	81	79	77	75	73	221	223	225	227	229	74	60	29
259	244	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	247	249	251	253	255	257	48	31
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{141, 142, \dots, 148, 149\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 435 \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{133, 134, \dots, 139, 140, D_{3 \times 3}, 150, 151, \dots, 156, 157\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 725 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{121, 122, \dots, 131, 132, D_{5 \times 5}, 158, 159, \dots, 168, 169\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 1015 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{105, 106, \dots, 119, 120, D_{7 \times 7}, 170, 171, \dots, 184, 185\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1305 \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{85, 86, \dots, 103, 104, D_{9 \times 9}, 186, 187, \dots, 204, 205\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 1595 \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{61, 62, \dots, 83, 84, D_{11 \times 11}, 206, 207, \dots, 228, 229\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 1885 \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{33, 34, \dots, 59, 60, D_{13 \times 13}, 230, 231, \dots, 256, 257\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 2175 \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 31, 32, D_{15 \times 15}, 258, 259, \dots, 288, 289\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 2465.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 17. These two ways are based on the magic squares of order 15 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.5 and 3.6.

2.5.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 225 by 33 to 257 in Example 3.5 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{15 \times 15}$ appearing in Example 2.5, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 given by

16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18
1	218	97	120	219	106	110	220	107	108	221	96	118	222	94	119	289
3	112	225	98	121	215	99	122	213	100	111	223	101	109	224	102	287
5	105	113	217	95	114	226	93	115	227	103	116	216	104	117	214	285
7	68	232	135	69	241	125	70	242	123	71	231	133	72	229	134	283
9	127	75	233	136	65	234	137	63	235	126	73	236	124	74	237	281
11	240	128	67	230	129	76	228	130	77	238	131	66	239	132	64	279
13	38	247	150	39	256	140	40	257	138	41	246	148	42	244	149	277
273	142	45	248	151	35	249	152	33	250	141	43	251	139	44	252	17
271	255	143	37	245	144	46	243	145	47	253	146	36	254	147	34	19
269	188	82	165	189	91	155	190	92	153	191	81	163	192	79	164	21
267	157	195	83	166	185	84	167	183	85	156	193	86	154	194	87	23
265	90	158	187	80	159	196	78	160	197	88	161	186	89	162	184	25
263	203	52	180	204	61	170	205	62	168	206	51	178	207	49	179	27
261	172	210	53	181	200	54	182	198	55	171	208	56	169	209	57	29
259	60	173	202	50	174	211	48	175	212	58	176	201	59	177	199	31
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 17, where the magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 2465, \quad S_{15 \times 15} := 2175 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 435.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** of order 3 with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.5.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 225 by 33 to 257 in Example 3.6 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{15 \times 15}$ appearing in Example 2.5, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 given by

16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18
1	33	250	62	151	229	63	220	107	136	199	78	190	122	166	169	289
3	152	241	34	243	55	137	211	64	213	100	167	181	79	183	115	287
5	244	48	145	242	46	214	93	130	212	76	184	108	160	182	91	285
7	235	47	256	49	138	205	77	226	94	123	175	92	196	109	153	283
9	61	139	228	40	257	106	124	198	70	227	121	154	168	85	197	281
11	35	249	60	149	232	65	219	105	134	202	80	189	120	164	172	279
13	150	239	37	245	54	135	209	67	215	99	165	179	82	185	114	277
273	247	50	144	240	44	217	95	129	210	74	187	110	159	180	89	17
271	234	45	254	52	140	204	75	224	97	125	174	90	194	112	155	19
269	59	142	230	39	255	104	127	200	69	225	119	157	170	84	195	21
267	36	251	58	147	233	66	221	103	132	203	81	191	118	162	173	23
265	148	237	38	246	56	133	207	68	216	101	163	177	83	186	116	25
263	248	51	146	238	42	218	96	131	208	72	188	111	161	178	87	27
261	236	43	252	53	141	206	73	222	98	126	176	88	192	113	156	29
259	57	143	231	41	253	102	128	201	71	223	117	158	171	86	193	31
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 17, where the magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 2465, \quad S_{15 \times 15} := 2175 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 435.$$

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic square** of order 5 with **equal magic sums**.

Summarizing, we have following result

Result 2.5. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 in two different ways. The **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 15, where each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square** with equal **semi-magic sums**;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 15, where each block of order 5 is a **pandiagonal magic square** with equal **magic sums**.*

2.6 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 19

Example 2.6. *Let's consider a **bordered magic square** of order 19 given by*

20	36	34	32	30	28	26	24	22	345	346	348	350	352	354	356	358	360	18
361	52	324	322	320	318	316	314	312	311	56	58	60	62	64	66	68	54	1
359	37	278	267	269	271	273	275	277	279	79	77	75	73	71	69	82	325	3
357	39	70	252	243	245	247	249	251	253	105	103	101	99	97	108	292	323	5
355	41	72	98	132	140	138	136	134	233	234	236	238	240	130	264	290	321	7
353	43	74	100	241	148	220	218	216	215	152	154	156	150	121	262	288	319	9
351	45	76	102	239	141	164	168	166	201	202	204	162	221	123	260	286	317	11
349	47	78	104	237	143	205	172	169	189	187	188	157	219	125	258	284	315	13
347	49	80	106	235	145	203	192	182	177	184	170	159	217	127	256	282	313	15
19	309	81	107	131	213	163	191	183	181	179	171	199	149	231	255	281	53	343
21	307	276	250	133	211	165	176	178	185	180	186	197	151	229	112	86	55	341
23	305	274	248	135	209	167	174	193	173	175	190	195	153	227	114	88	57	339
25	303	272	246	137	207	200	194	196	161	160	158	198	155	225	116	90	59	337
27	301	270	244	139	212	142	144	146	147	210	208	206	214	223	118	92	61	335
29	299	268	242	232	222	224	226	228	129	128	126	124	122	230	120	94	63	333
31	297	266	254	119	117	115	113	111	109	257	259	261	263	265	110	96	65	331
33	295	280	95	93	91	89	87	85	83	283	285	287	289	291	293	84	67	329
35	308	38	40	42	44	46	48	50	51	306	304	302	300	298	296	294	310	327
344	326	328	330	332	334	336	338	340	17	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	342

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{177, 178, \dots, 184, 185\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 543 \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{169, 170, \dots, 215, 216, D_{3 \times 3}, 186, 187, \dots, 192, 193\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 905 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{157, 158, \dots, 167, 168, D_{5 \times 5}, 194, 195, \dots, 204, 205\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 1267 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{141, 142, \dots, 155, 156, D_{7 \times 7}, 206, 207, \dots, 220, 221\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 1629 \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{121, 122, \dots, 139, 140, D_{9 \times 9}, 222, 223, \dots, 240, 241\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 1991 \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{97, 98, \dots, 119, 120, D_{11 \times 11}, 242, 243, \dots, 264, 265\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 2353 \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{69, 70, \dots, 95, 96, D_{13 \times 13}, 266, 267, \dots, 292, 293\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 2715 \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{37, 38, \dots, 67, 68, D_{15 \times 15}, 294, 295, \dots, 324, 325\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 3077 \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 35, 36, D_{17 \times 17}, 326, 327, \dots, 360, 361\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 3439.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 17. These two ways are based on the magic squares of order 15 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.5 and 3.6.

2.6.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 225 by 69 to 293 in Example 3.5 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{15 \times 15}$ appearing in Example 2.6, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 given by

20	36	34	32	30	28	26	24	22	345	346	348	350	352	354	356	358	360	18
361	52	324	322	320	318	316	314	312	311	56	58	60	62	64	66	68	54	1
359	37	254	133	156	255	142	146	256	143	144	257	132	154	258	130	155	325	3
357	39	148	261	134	157	251	135	158	249	136	147	259	137	145	260	138	323	5
355	41	141	149	253	131	150	262	129	151	263	139	152	252	140	153	250	321	7
353	43	104	268	171	105	277	161	106	278	159	107	267	169	108	265	170	319	9
351	45	163	111	269	172	101	270	173	99	271	162	109	272	160	110	273	317	11
349	47	276	164	103	266	165	112	264	166	113	274	167	102	275	168	100	315	13
347	49	74	283	186	75	292	176	76	293	174	77	282	184	78	280	185	313	15
19	309	178	81	284	187	71	285	188	69	286	177	79	287	175	80	288	53	343
21	307	291	179	73	281	180	82	279	181	83	289	182	72	290	183	70	55	341
23	305	224	118	201	225	127	191	226	128	189	227	117	199	228	115	200	57	339
25	303	193	231	119	202	221	120	203	219	121	192	229	122	190	230	123	59	337
27	301	126	194	223	116	195	232	114	196	233	124	197	222	125	198	220	61	335
29	299	239	88	216	240	97	206	241	98	204	242	87	214	243	85	215	63	333
31	297	208	246	89	217	236	90	218	234	91	207	244	92	205	245	93	65	331
33	295	96	209	238	86	210	247	84	211	248	94	212	237	95	213	235	67	329
35	308	38	40	42	44	46	48	50	51	306	304	302	300	298	296	294	310	327
344	326	328	330	332	334	336	338	340	17	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	342

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19, where magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 3439, \quad S_{17 \times 17} := 3077 \quad S_{15 \times 15} := 2715 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 543.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** of order 3 with **equal magic sums**.

2.6.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 225 by 69 to 293 in Example 3.6 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{15 \times 15}$ appearing in Example 2.6, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 given by

20	36	34	32	30	28	26	24	22	345	346	348	350	352	354	356	358	360	18
361	52	324	322	320	318	316	314	312	311	56	58	60	62	64	66	68	54	1
359	37	69	286	98	187	265	99	256	143	172	235	114	226	158	202	205	325	3
357	39	188	277	70	279	91	173	247	100	249	136	203	217	115	219	151	323	5
355	41	280	84	181	278	82	250	129	166	248	112	220	144	196	218	127	321	7
353	43	271	83	292	85	174	241	113	262	130	159	211	128	232	145	189	319	9
351	45	97	175	264	76	293	142	160	234	106	263	157	190	204	121	233	317	11
349	47	71	285	96	185	268	101	255	141	170	238	116	225	156	200	208	315	13
347	49	186	275	73	281	90	171	245	103	251	135	201	215	118	221	150	313	15
19	309	283	86	180	276	80	253	131	165	246	110	223	146	195	216	125	53	343
21	307	270	81	290	88	176	240	111	260	133	161	210	126	230	148	191	55	341
23	305	95	178	266	75	291	140	163	236	105	261	155	193	206	120	231	57	339
25	303	72	287	94	183	269	102	257	139	168	239	117	227	154	198	209	59	337
27	301	184	273	74	282	92	169	243	104	252	137	199	213	119	222	152	61	335
29	299	284	87	182	274	78	254	132	167	244	108	224	147	197	214	123	63	333
31	297	272	79	288	89	177	242	109	258	134	162	212	124	228	149	192	65	331
33	295	93	179	267	77	289	138	164	237	107	259	153	194	207	122	229	67	329
35	308	38	40	42	44	46	48	50	51	306	304	302	300	298	296	294	310	327
344	326	328	330	332	334	336	338	340	17	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	342

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 19, where the magic square of order 15 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 3439, \quad S_{17 \times 17} := 3077 \quad S_{15 \times 15} := 2715 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 905.$$

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 with **equal magic sum**.

Summarizing, we have following result

Result 2.6. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 in two different ways. The **block-wise** magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 15, where each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square** with equal **semi-magic sums**;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 15, where each block of order 5 is a **pandiagonal magic square** with equal **magic sums**.*

The process applied here is the same as in case of magic square of order 17, but with different entries.

2.7 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 22

Example 2.7. Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 22 given by

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	423	415	69	417	67	419	420	64	63	52	71	425	426	58	428	56	430	54	432	61	452
451	72	387	105	381	103	383	101	385	99	396	81	389	95	391	93	393	91	395	97	413	34
35	412	378	355	349	135	351	352	132	131	122	137	357	358	126	360	124	362	129	107	73	450
449	74	108	138	327	163	323	161	325	159	334	145	329	155	331	153	333	157	347	377	411	36
37	410	376	346	320	303	299	300	184	183	176	187	305	306	178	308	181	165	139	109	75	448
447	76	110	140	166	188	283	278	208	276	210	206	196	290	194	284	297	319	345	375	409	38
39	408	374	344	318	296	205	268	273	213	211	224	262	222	267	280	189	167	141	111	77	446
445	78	112	142	168	190	281	265	255	231	258	225	257	229	220	204	295	317	343	373	407	40
41	406	372	342	316	294	203	266	252	248	235	238	249	233	219	282	191	169	143	113	79	444
443	80	114	144	170	192	288	271	234	241	246	243	240	251	214	197	293	315	341	371	405	42
453	43	106	115	164	171	193	221	232	245	242	239	244	253	264	292	314	321	370	379	442	32
475	51	88	121	150	175	285	216	226	236	247	250	237	259	269	200	310	335	364	397	434	10
9	435	398	365	336	311	199	215	256	254	227	260	228	230	270	286	174	149	120	87	50	476
477	49	86	119	148	173	287	218	212	272	274	261	223	263	217	198	312	337	366	399	436	8
7	437	400	367	338	313	201	207	277	209	275	279	289	195	291	202	172	147	118	85	48	478
479	47	84	117	146	304	186	185	301	302	309	298	180	179	307	177	182	339	368	401	438	6
5	439	402	369	328	322	162	324	160	326	151	340	156	330	154	332	152	158	116	83	46	480
481	45	82	356	136	350	134	133	353	354	363	348	128	127	359	125	361	123	130	403	440	4
3	441	388	380	104	382	102	384	100	386	89	404	96	390	94	392	92	394	90	98	44	482
483	424	70	416	68	418	66	65	421	422	433	414	60	59	427	57	429	55	431	53	62	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{235, 236, \dots, 249, 250\}; & S_{4 \times 4} &:= 970 \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{225, 226, \dots, 233, 234, D_{4 \times 4}, 251, 252, \dots, 259, 260\}; & S_{6 \times 6} &:= 1455 \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{211, 212, \dots, 223, 224, D_{6 \times 6}, 261, 262, \dots, 273, 274\}; & S_{8 \times 8} &:= 1940 \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{193, 194, \dots, 209, 210, D_{8 \times 8}, 275, 276, \dots, 291, 292\}; & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 2425 \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{171, 172, \dots, 191, 192, D_{10 \times 10}, 293, 294, \dots, 313, 314\}; & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 2910 \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{145, 146, \dots, 169, 170, D_{12 \times 12}, 315, 316, \dots, 339, 340\}; & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 3395 \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{115, 116, \dots, 285, 287, D_{14 \times 14}, 341, 342, \dots, 369, 370\}; & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 3880 \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{81, 82, \dots, 113, 114, D_{16 \times 16}, 371, 372, \dots, 403, 404\}; & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 4365 \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{43, 44, \dots, 79, 80, D_{18 \times 18}, 405, 406, \dots, 441, 442\}; & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 4850 \\
 D_{22 \times 22} &:= \{1, 3, \dots, 41, 42, D_{20 \times 20}, 443, 444, \dots, 483, 484\}; & S_{22 \times 22} &:= 5335.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are six different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 22. These six ways are based on the magic squares of orders 20, 18 and 16 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.12, 3.13, 3.15, 3.9, 3.11 and 3.8.

2.7.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 400 by 43 to 442 in Example 3.12 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{20 \times 20}$ appearing in Example 2.7, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 given by

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	232	243	62	433	209	266	79	416	191	284	101	394	168	307	118	377	150	325	140	355	452
451	53	442	223	252	76	419	206	269	94	401	184	291	117	378	167	308	135	360	145	330	34
35	423	52	253	242	406	69	276	219	384	91	294	201	367	108	317	178	345	130	335	160	450
449	262	233	432	43	279	216	409	66	301	194	391	84	318	177	368	107	340	155	350	125	36
37	171	304	121	374	148	327	138	357	230	245	60	435	212	263	82	413	189	286	99	396	448
447	114	381	164	311	137	358	147	328	55	440	225	250	73	422	203	272	96	399	186	289	38
39	364	111	314	181	347	128	337	158	425	50	255	240	403	72	273	222	386	89	296	199	446
445	321	174	371	104	338	157	348	127	260	235	430	45	282	213	412	63	299	196	389	86	40
41	210	265	80	415	192	283	102	393	169	306	119	376	151	324	141	354	228	247	58	437	444
443	75	420	205	270	93	402	183	292	116	379	166	309	134	361	144	331	57	438	227	248	42
453	405	70	275	220	383	92	293	202	366	109	316	179	344	131	334	161	427	48	257	238	32
475	280	215	410	65	302	193	392	83	319	176	369	106	341	154	351	124	258	237	428	47	10
9	149	326	139	356	231	244	61	434	208	267	78	417	190	285	100	395	172	303	122	373	476
477	136	359	146	329	54	441	224	251	77	418	207	268	95	400	185	290	113	382	163	312	8
7	346	129	336	159	424	51	254	241	407	68	277	218	385	90	295	200	363	112	313	182	478
479	339	156	349	126	261	234	431	44	278	217	408	67	300	195	390	85	322	173	372	103	6
5	188	287	98	397	170	305	120	375	152	323	142	353	229	246	59	436	211	264	81	414	480
481	97	398	187	288	115	380	165	310	133	362	143	332	56	439	226	249	74	421	204	271	4
3	387	88	297	198	365	110	315	180	343	132	333	162	426	49	256	239	404	71	274	221	482
483	298	197	388	87	320	175	370	105	342	153	352	123	259	236	429	46	281	214	411	64	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22, where magic square of order 20 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5335, \quad S_{20 \times 20} := 4850 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 970.$$

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with **equal magic sums**.

2.7.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 400 by 43 to 442 in Example 3.13 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{20 \times 20}$ appearing in Example 2.7, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 given by

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	49	177	225	353	401	54	182	230	358	406	43	171	219	347	395	56	184	232	360	408	452
451	305	433	81	129	257	310	438	86	134	262	299	427	75	123	251	312	440	88	136	264	34
35	161	209	337	385	113	166	214	342	390	118	155	203	331	379	107	168	216	344	392	120	450
449	417	65	193	241	289	422	70	198	246	294	411	59	187	235	283	424	72	200	248	296	36
37	273	321	369	97	145	278	326	374	102	150	267	315	363	91	139	280	328	376	104	152	448
447	44	172	220	348	396	55	183	231	359	407	50	178	226	354	402	53	181	229	357	405	38
39	300	428	76	124	252	311	439	87	135	263	306	434	82	130	258	309	437	85	133	261	446
445	156	204	332	380	108	167	215	343	391	119	162	210	338	386	114	165	213	341	389	117	40
41	412	60	188	236	284	423	71	199	247	295	418	66	194	242	290	421	69	197	245	293	444
443	268	316	364	92	140	279	327	375	103	151	274	322	370	98	146	277	325	373	101	149	42
453	58	186	234	362	410	45	173	221	349	397	52	180	228	356	404	47	175	223	351	399	32
475	314	442	90	138	266	301	429	77	125	253	308	436	84	132	260	303	431	79	127	255	10
9	170	218	346	394	122	157	205	333	381	109	164	212	340	388	116	159	207	335	383	111	476
477	426	74	202	250	298	413	61	189	237	285	420	68	196	244	292	415	63	191	239	287	8
7	282	330	378	106	154	269	317	365	93	141	276	324	372	100	148	271	319	367	95	143	478
479	51	179	227	355	403	48	176	224	352	400	57	185	233	361	409	46	174	222	350	398	6
5	307	435	83	131	259	304	432	80	128	256	313	441	89	137	265	302	430	78	126	254	480
481	163	211	339	387	115	160	208	336	384	112	169	217	345	393	121	158	206	334	382	110	4
3	419	67	195	243	291	416	64	192	240	288	425	73	201	249	297	414	62	190	238	286	482
483	275	323	371	99	147	272	320	368	96	144	281	329	377	105	153	270	318	366	94	142	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22, where the magic square of order 20 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5335 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{20 \times 20} := 4850.$$

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 5 with **different magic sums**.

2.7.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 400 by 43 to 442 in Example 3.15 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{20 \times 20}$ appearing in Example 2.7, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 given by

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	43	219	114	426	378	130	351	195	282	287	44	220	113	425	377	129	352	196	281	288	452
451	194	106	298	367	142	439	203	270	51	355	193	105	297	368	141	440	204	269	52	356	34
35	286	278	127	222	434	55	199	363	350	111	285	277	128	221	433	56	200	364	349	112	450
449	122	375	271	190	343	207	438	46	294	139	121	376	272	189	344	208	437	45	293	140	36
37	430	123	59	275	211	346	374	302	107	198	429	124	60	276	212	345	373	301	108	197	448
447	371	290	183	359	115	274	62	427	138	206	372	289	184	360	116	273	61	428	137	205	38
39	218	47	362	134	266	191	295	119	423	370	217	48	361	133	265	192	296	120	424	369	446
445	135	431	210	103	299	382	267	358	186	54	136	432	209	104	300	381	268	357	185	53	40
41	347	202	435	291	50	118	126	214	379	263	348	201	436	292	49	117	125	213	380	264	444
443	279	354	366	58	187	283	110	131	215	442	280	353	365	57	188	284	109	132	216	441	42
453	63	239	94	406	398	150	331	175	262	307	64	240	93	405	397	149	332	176	261	308	32
475	174	86	318	387	162	419	223	250	71	335	173	85	317	388	161	420	224	249	72	336	10
9	306	258	147	242	414	75	179	383	330	91	305	257	148	241	413	76	180	384	329	92	476
477	102	395	251	170	323	227	418	66	314	159	101	396	252	169	324	228	417	65	313	160	8
7	410	143	79	255	231	326	394	322	87	178	409	144	80	256	232	325	393	321	88	177	478
479	391	310	163	339	95	254	82	407	158	226	392	309	164	340	96	253	81	408	157	225	6
5	238	67	342	154	246	171	315	99	403	390	237	68	341	153	245	172	316	100	404	389	480
481	155	411	230	83	319	402	247	338	166	74	156	412	229	84	320	401	248	337	165	73	4
3	327	182	415	311	70	98	146	234	399	243	328	181	416	312	69	97	145	233	400	244	482
483	259	334	386	78	167	303	90	151	235	422	260	333	385	77	168	304	89	152	236	421	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 with following sums:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5335, \quad S_{20 \times 20} := 4850 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{10 \times 10} := 2425.$$

Blocks of order 10 are **magic squares** of order 10 with **equal magic sum**.

2.7.4 Forth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 400 by 43 to 442 in Example 3.9 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{18 \times 18}$ appearing in Example 2.7, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 given by

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	423	415	69	417	67	419	420	64	63	52	71	425	426	58	428	56	430	54	432	61	452
451	72	99	119	82	273	257	292	326	342	307	380	360	397	219	239	202	158	138	175	413	34
35	412	83	100	117	293	274	255	306	325	344	396	379	362	203	220	237	174	157	140	73	450
449	74	118	81	101	256	291	275	343	308	324	361	398	378	238	201	221	139	176	156	411	36
37	410	327	347	310	153	137	172	381	365	400	212	228	193	267	251	286	111	131	94	75	448
447	76	311	328	345	173	154	135	401	382	363	192	211	230	287	268	249	95	112	129	409	38
39	408	346	309	329	136	171	155	364	399	383	229	194	210	250	285	269	130	93	113	77	446
445	78	170	150	187	116	132	97	207	227	190	321	341	304	369	353	388	272	252	289	407	40
41	406	186	169	152	96	115	134	191	208	225	305	322	339	389	370	351	288	271	254	79	444
443	80	151	188	168	133	98	114	226	189	209	340	303	323	352	387	371	253	290	270	405	42
453	43	374	354	391	218	234	199	110	126	91	278	258	295	164	144	181	315	335	298	442	32
475	51	390	373	356	198	217	236	90	109	128	294	277	260	180	163	146	299	316	333	434	10
9	435	355	392	372	235	200	216	127	92	108	259	296	276	145	182	162	334	297	317	50	476
477	49	261	245	280	375	359	394	165	149	184	105	125	88	332	348	313	213	233	196	436	8
7	437	281	262	243	395	376	357	185	166	147	89	106	123	312	331	350	197	214	231	48	478
479	47	244	279	263	358	393	377	148	183	167	124	87	107	349	314	330	232	195	215	438	6
5	439	224	240	205	320	336	301	266	246	283	159	143	178	104	120	85	386	366	403	46	480
481	45	204	223	242	300	319	338	282	265	248	179	160	141	84	103	122	402	385	368	440	4
3	441	241	206	222	337	302	318	247	284	264	142	177	161	121	86	102	367	404	384	44	482
483	424	70	416	68	418	66	65	421	422	433	414	60	59	427	57	429	55	431	53	62	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 with following sums:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5335, \quad S_{20 \times 20} := 4850 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{18 \times 18} := 4365.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **magic squares** of order 3 with **different magic sums**.

2.7.5 Fifth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 400 by 43 to 442 in Example 3.12 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{18 \times 18}$ appearing in Example 2.7, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 given by

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	423	415	69	417	67	419	420	64	63	52	71	425	426	58	428	56	430	54	432	61	452
451	72	84	390	383	372	95	131	89	395	378	377	90	126	82	388	385	370	97	133	413	34
35	412	347	149	329	156	174	300	342	144	324	161	179	305	349	151	331	154	172	298	73	450
449	74	293	282	210	221	257	192	288	287	215	216	252	197	295	280	208	223	259	190	411	36
37	410	239	203	264	275	228	246	234	198	269	270	233	251	241	205	262	277	226	244	75	448
447	76	138	311	167	318	336	185	143	306	162	323	341	180	136	313	169	316	334	187	409	38
39	408	354	120	102	113	365	401	359	125	107	108	360	396	352	118	100	115	367	403	77	446
445	78	83	389	384	371	96	132	85	391	382	373	94	130	87	393	380	375	92	128	407	40
41	406	348	150	330	155	173	299	346	148	328	157	175	301	344	146	326	159	177	303	79	444
443	80	294	281	209	222	258	191	292	283	211	220	256	193	290	285	213	218	254	195	405	42
453	43	240	204	263	276	227	245	238	202	265	274	229	247	236	200	267	272	231	249	442	32
475	51	137	312	168	317	335	186	139	310	166	319	337	184	141	308	164	321	339	182	434	10
9	435	353	119	101	114	366	402	355	121	103	112	364	400	357	123	105	110	362	398	50	476
477	49	88	394	379	376	91	127	81	387	386	369	98	134	86	392	381	374	93	129	436	8
7	437	343	145	325	160	178	304	350	152	332	153	171	297	345	147	327	158	176	302	48	478
479	47	289	286	214	217	253	196	296	279	207	224	260	189	291	284	212	219	255	194	438	6
5	439	235	199	268	271	232	250	242	206	261	278	225	243	237	201	266	273	230	248	46	480
481	45	142	307	163	322	340	181	135	314	170	315	333	188	140	309	165	320	338	183	440	4
3	441	358	124	106	109	361	397	351	117	99	116	368	404	356	122	104	111	363	399	44	482
483	424	70	416	68	418	66	65	421	422	433	414	60	59	427	57	429	55	431	53	62	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 with following sums:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5335, \quad S_{20 \times 20} := 4850, \quad S_{18 \times 18} := 4365 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 1455$$

Blocks of order 6 are **magic squares** of order 6 with **equal magic sums**.

2.7.6 Sixth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 256 by 115 to 370 in Example 3.8 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{16 \times 16}$ appearing in Example 2.7, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 given by

21	473	13	471	15	469	17	467	19	465	1	474	23	461	25	459	27	457	29	455	31	463
33	423	415	69	417	67	419	420	64	63	52	71	425	426	58	428	56	430	54	432	61	452
451	72	387	105	381	103	383	101	385	99	396	81	389	95	391	93	393	91	395	97	413	34
35	412	378	115	268	353	234	137	258	363	212	158	293	312	207	176	279	326	189	107	73	450
449	74	108	346	241	124	259	356	219	146	249	319	200	149	302	333	182	167	288	377	411	36
37	410	376	236	339	266	129	226	361	244	139	197	318	303	152	183	336	285	166	109	75	448
447	76	110	273	122	227	348	251	132	217	370	296	159	206	309	278	173	192	327	375	409	38
39	408	374	160	295	310	205	174	277	328	191	121	274	347	228	131	252	369	218	111	77	446
445	78	112	317	198	151	304	335	184	165	286	340	235	130	265	362	225	140	243	373	407	40
41	406	372	199	320	301	150	181	334	287	168	242	345	260	123	220	355	250	145	113	79	444
443	80	114	294	157	208	311	280	175	190	325	267	116	233	354	257	138	211	364	371	405	42
453	43	106	169	290	331	180	147	300	321	202	144	247	358	221	126	261	344	239	379	442	32
475	51	88	324	187	178	281	314	209	156	291	365	214	135	256	351	232	117	270	397	434	10
9	435	398	194	329	276	171	204	307	298	161	215	368	253	134	229	350	271	120	87	50	476
477	49	86	283	164	185	338	305	154	195	316	246	141	224	359	264	127	238	341	399	436	8
7	437	400	142	245	360	223	128	263	342	237	163	284	337	186	153	306	315	196	85	48	478
479	47	84	367	216	133	254	349	230	119	272	330	193	172	275	308	203	162	297	401	438	6
5	439	402	213	366	255	136	231	352	269	118	188	323	282	177	210	313	292	155	83	46	480
481	45	82	248	143	222	357	262	125	240	343	289	170	179	332	299	148	201	322	403	440	4
3	441	388	380	104	382	102	384	100	386	89	404	96	390	94	392	92	394	90	98	44	482
483	424	70	416	68	418	66	65	421	422	433	414	60	59	427	57	429	55	431	53	62	2
22	12	472	14	470	16	468	18	466	20	484	11	462	24	460	26	458	28	456	30	454	464

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 22, where the magic square of order 16 is **bimagic square** with following sums:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5335, \quad S_{20 \times 20} := 4850, \quad S_{18 \times 18} := 4365, \quad S_{16 \times 16} := 3880 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 970$$

Blocks of order 4 are **magic squares** of order 4 with **equal magic sums**. Moreover, magic square of order 16 is a **bimagic square** with **bimagic sum** $Sb_{16 \times 16} := 1028280$.

Summarizing, we have following result

Result 2.7. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 22 in six different ways. The blocks are considered as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 20, where blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 20, where blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **different magic sums**;*

- (iii) Magic square of 20, where blocks order 10 are magic squares with equal magic sums;
- (iv) Magic square of 18, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sum;
- (v) Magic square of 18, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;
- (vi) Bimagic square of 16, where block of order 4 are magic square with equal magic sums.

2.8 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 23

Example 2.8. Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 23 given by

508	43	41	39	37	35	33	31	29	27	25	23	511	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	527	529	24
486	464	447	449	451	453	455	457	459	461	463	465	61	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	45	64	44
488	46	428	119	117	115	113	111	109	107	105	103	431	433	435	437	439	441	443	445	104	484	42
490	48	410	394	151	149	147	145	143	141	139	137	397	399	401	403	405	407	409	138	120	482	40
492	50	412	378	364	350	352	354	356	358	360	165	164	162	160	158	156	154	362	152	118	480	38
494	52	414	380	179	192	181	183	185	187	189	337	335	333	331	329	327	336	351	150	116	478	36
496	54	416	382	177	348	214	205	207	209	211	315	313	311	309	307	314	182	353	148	114	476	34
498	56	418	384	175	346	324	296	226	228	230	231	294	292	290	298	206	184	355	146	112	474	32
500	58	420	386	173	344	322	291	282	242	244	245	280	278	284	239	208	186	357	144	110	472	30
502	60	422	388	171	342	320	293	279	274	270	255	254	272	251	237	210	188	359	142	108	470	28
504	62	424	390	169	340	318	295	281	259	262	267	266	271	249	235	212	190	361	140	106	468	26
21	63	101	135	167	339	317	297	283	257	269	265	261	273	247	233	213	191	363	395	429	467	509
20	462	100	134	367	196	218	229	243	277	264	263	268	253	287	301	312	334	163	396	430	68	510
18	460	98	132	369	198	220	227	241	258	260	275	276	256	289	303	310	332	161	398	432	70	512
16	458	96	130	371	200	222	225	246	288	286	285	250	252	248	305	308	330	159	400	434	72	514
14	456	94	128	373	202	224	232	304	302	300	299	236	238	240	234	306	328	157	402	436	74	516
12	454	92	126	375	204	216	325	323	321	319	215	217	219	221	223	316	326	155	404	438	76	518
10	452	90	124	377	194	349	347	345	343	341	193	195	197	199	201	203	338	153	406	440	78	520
8	450	88	122	168	180	178	176	174	172	170	365	366	368	370	372	374	376	166	408	442	80	522
6	448	86	392	379	381	383	385	387	389	391	393	133	131	129	127	125	123	121	136	444	82	524
4	446	426	411	413	415	417	419	421	423	425	427	99	97	95	93	91	89	87	85	102	84	526
2	466	83	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	65	469	471	473	475	477	479	481	483	485	66	528
506	487	489	491	493	495	497	499	501	503	505	507	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1	22

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{261, 262, 263, 264, 265, 266, 267, 268, 269\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 795 \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{253, 254, \dots, 259, 260, D_{3 \times 3}, 270, 271, \dots, 276, 277\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 1325 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{241, 242, \dots, 251, 252, D_{5 \times 5}, 278, 279, \dots, 288, 289\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 1855 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{225, 226, \dots, 239, 240, D_{7 \times 7}, 290, 291, \dots, 304, 305\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 2385
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{205, 206, \dots, 223, 224, D_{9 \times 9}, 306, 307, \dots, 334, 325\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 2915 \\ D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{181, 182, \dots, 203, 204, D_{11 \times 11}, 326, 327, \dots, 348, 349\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 3445 \\ D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{153, 154, \dots, 179, 180, D_{13 \times 13}, 350, 351, \dots, 376, 377\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 3975 \\ D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{121, 122, \dots, 151, 152, D_{15 \times 15}, 378, 379, \dots, 408, 409\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 4505 \\ D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{85, 86, \dots, 119, 120, D_{17 \times 17}, 410, 411, \dots, 444, 445\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 5035 \\ D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{45, 46, \dots, 83, 84, D_{19 \times 19}, 446, 447, \dots, 484, 485\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 5565 \\ D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 43, 44, D_{21 \times 21}, 486, 487, \dots, 528, 529\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 6095. \end{aligned}$$

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 23. These two ways are based on the magic squares of orders 21 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.16 and 3.17.

2.8.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 441 by 44 to 485 in Example 3.16 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{21 \times 21}$ appearing in Example 2.8, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 given by

508	43	41	39	37	35	33	31	29	27	25	23	511	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	527	529	24
486	290	155	350	318	419	58	231	133	431	256	463	76	212	111	472	299	397	99	249	177	369	44
488	344	287	164	62	331	402	427	221	147	85	265	445	468	199	128	103	309	383	366	243	186	42
490	161	353	281	415	45	335	137	441	217	454	67	274	115	485	195	393	89	313	180	375	240	40
492	317	384	94	236	187	372	291	156	348	332	407	56	213	146	436	273	448	74	193	127	475	38
494	90	304	401	376	246	173	345	285	165	50	329	416	440	226	129	70	263	462	484	202	109	36
496	388	107	300	183	362	250	159	354	282	413	59	323	142	423	230	452	84	259	118	466	211	34
498	255	461	79	210	112	473	298	400	97	254	174	367	278	166	351	333	408	54	227	134	434	32
500	83	268	444	469	200	126	106	307	382	363	241	191	355	288	152	51	327	417	428	224	143	30
502	457	66	272	116	483	196	391	88	316	178	380	237	162	341	292	411	60	324	140	437	218	28
504	320	418	57	228	135	432	269	449	77	192	125	478	315	385	95	235	190	370	296	153	346	26
21	61	330	404	429	222	144	71	266	458	482	205	108	91	305	399	379	244	172	342	283	170	509
20	414	47	334	138	438	219	455	80	260	121	465	209	389	105	301	181	361	253	157	359	279	510
18	252	175	368	277	169	349	338	405	52	215	145	435	270	450	75	206	113	476	297	398	100	512
16	364	242	189	358	286	151	48	325	422	439	225	131	72	264	459	470	203	122	104	310	381	514
14	179	378	238	160	340	295	409	65	321	141	425	229	453	81	261	119	479	197	394	87	314	516
12	207	114	474	311	386	98	234	188	373	294	154	347	319	421	55	233	132	430	257	460	78	518
10	471	201	123	92	308	395	377	247	171	343	284	168	64	328	403	426	220	149	82	267	446	520
8	117	480	198	392	101	302	184	360	251	158	357	280	412	46	337	136	443	216	456	68	271	522
6	214	148	433	275	447	73	194	124	477	312	387	96	248	176	371	276	167	352	336	406	53	524
4	442	223	130	69	262	464	481	204	110	93	306	396	365	245	185	356	289	150	49	326	420	526
2	139	424	232	451	86	258	120	467	208	390	102	303	182	374	239	163	339	293	410	63	322	528
506	487	489	491	493	495	497	499	501	503	505	507	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1	22

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23, where the magic square of order 21 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 6095, \quad S_{21 \times 21} := 5565 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 795$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic square** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.8.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 441 by 44 to 485 in Example 3.17 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{21 \times 21}$ appearing in Example 2.8, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 given by

508	43	41	39	37	35	33	31	29	27	25	23	511	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	527	529	24
486	45	155	199	287	309	419	441	47	154	198	286	310	418	442	46	153	200	285	311	417	443	44
488	414	440	63	150	197	283	308	415	439	64	152	196	282	307	416	438	65	151	195	284	306	42
490	281	304	413	435	62	168	192	280	303	412	436	61	169	194	279	305	411	437	60	170	193	40
492	167	210	276	302	409	434	57	166	211	278	301	408	433	58	165	212	277	300	410	432	59	38
494	430	56	162	209	294	297	407	429	55	163	208	295	299	406	431	54	164	207	296	298	405	36
496	315	402	428	52	161	204	293	316	404	427	51	160	205	292	317	403	426	53	159	206	291	34
498	203	288	314	420	423	50	157	202	289	313	421	425	49	156	201	290	312	422	424	48	158	32
500	87	134	178	266	330	398	462	89	133	177	265	331	397	463	88	132	179	264	332	396	464	30
502	393	461	105	129	176	262	329	394	460	106	131	175	261	328	395	459	107	130	174	263	327	28
504	260	325	392	456	104	147	171	259	324	391	457	103	148	173	258	326	390	458	102	149	172	26
21	146	189	255	323	388	455	99	145	190	257	322	387	454	100	144	191	256	321	389	453	101	509
20	451	98	141	188	273	318	386	450	97	142	187	274	320	385	452	96	143	186	275	319	384	510
18	336	381	449	94	140	183	272	337	383	448	93	139	184	271	338	382	447	95	138	185	270	512
16	182	267	335	399	444	92	136	181	268	334	400	446	91	135	180	269	333	401	445	90	137	514
14	66	113	220	245	351	377	483	68	112	219	244	352	376	484	67	111	221	243	353	375	485	516
12	372	482	84	108	218	241	350	373	481	85	110	217	240	349	374	480	86	109	216	242	348	518
10	239	346	371	477	83	126	213	238	345	370	478	82	127	215	237	347	369	479	81	128	214	520
8	125	231	234	344	367	476	78	124	232	236	343	366	475	79	123	233	235	342	368	474	80	522
6	472	77	120	230	252	339	365	471	76	121	229	253	341	364	473	75	122	228	254	340	363	524
4	357	360	470	73	119	225	251	358	362	469	72	118	226	250	359	361	468	74	117	227	249	526
2	224	246	356	378	465	71	115	223	247	355	379	467	70	114	222	248	354	380	466	69	116	528
506	487	489	491	493	495	497	499	501	503	505	507	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1	22

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 23, where the magic square of order 21 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 6095, \quad S_{21 \times 21} := 5565 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{7 \times 7} := 795$$

Blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

Summarizing, we have following result

Result 2.8. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 in two different ways. The block-wise magic squares considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 21, where each block of order 3 is a semi-magic square with equal semi-magic sums;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 21, where each block of order 7 is a pandiagonal magic square with equal magic sum.*

2.9 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 26

Example 2.9. Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 26 given by

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	74	63	613	65	611	67	609	69	607	71	72	592	615	602	601	77	78	598	80	596	82	594	84	604	638
637	52	559	548	130	546	132	544	134	542	136	540	138	128	106	572	104	574	102	576	100	578	98	560	625	40
41	624	127	157	528	150	526	152	524	154	522	521	167	148	159	160	516	515	163	513	165	511	519	550	53	636
635	54	551	509	483	201	477	199	479	197	481	195	492	177	485	191	487	189	489	187	491	193	168	126	623	42
43	622	125	169	474	225	443	235	441	237	439	239	437	466	460	216	462	214	464	212	226	203	508	552	55	634
633	56	553	507	204	458	253	429	249	427	251	425	241	430	255	421	257	419	259	423	219	473	170	124	621	44
45	620	123	171	472	220	261	400	282	281	397	398	405	394	276	275	403	273	278	416	457	205	506	554	57	632
631	58	555	505	206	456	415	409	380	376	300	378	293	388	296	382	294	298	268	262	221	471	172	122	619	46
47	618	121	173	470	222	263	269	290	363	316	315	310	360	365	366	313	387	408	414	455	207	504	556	59	630
629	60	557	503	208	454	413	407	386	318	352	350	323	356	324	326	359	291	270	264	223	469	174	120	617	48
49	616	119	175	468	453	265	271	292	358	322	332	341	337	344	355	319	385	406	412	224	209	502	558	61	628
627	626	570	501	210	233	411	267	302	320	328	343	338	342	331	349	357	375	410	266	444	467	176	107	51	50
639	581	97	538	202	218	417	288	306	307	330	346	335	339	334	347	370	371	389	260	459	475	139	580	96	38
665	95	561	530	184	227	431	390	372	309	348	333	340	336	345	329	368	305	287	246	450	493	147	116	582	12
11	583	115	146	494	228	245	286	304	369	351	327	354	321	353	325	308	373	391	432	449	183	531	562	94	666
667	93	563	532	182	448	433	392	374	364	361	362	367	317	312	311	314	303	285	244	229	495	145	114	584	10
9	585	113	144	496	447	243	284	379	301	377	299	384	289	381	295	383	297	393	434	230	181	533	564	92	668
669	91	565	534	180	231	435	399	395	396	280	279	272	283	401	402	274	404	277	242	446	497	143	112	586	8
7	587	111	142	498	445	254	248	428	250	426	252	436	247	422	256	420	258	418	424	232	179	535	566	90	670
671	89	567	536	178	451	234	442	236	440	238	438	240	211	217	461	215	463	213	465	452	499	141	110	588	6
5	589	109	140	484	476	200	478	198	480	196	482	185	500	192	486	190	488	188	490	186	194	537	568	88	672
673	87	569	158	149	527	151	525	153	523	155	156	510	529	518	517	161	162	514	164	512	166	520	108	590	4
3	591	117	129	547	131	545	133	543	135	541	137	539	549	571	105	573	103	575	101	577	99	579	118	86	674
675	73	614	64	612	66	610	68	608	70	606	605	85	62	75	76	600	599	79	597	81	595	83	593	603	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{331, 332, \dots, 345, 346\}; & S_{4 \times 4} &:= 1354 \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{321, 322, \dots, 329, 330, D_{4 \times 4}, 347, 348, \dots, 355, 356\}; & S_{6 \times 6} &:= 2031 \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{289, 290, \dots, 305, 306, D_{6 \times 6}, 357, 358, \dots, 369, 370\}; & S_{8 \times 8} &:= 2708 \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{267, 268, \dots, 315, 316, D_{8 \times 8}, 371, 372, \dots, 367, 388\}; & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 3385 \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{217, 218, \dots, 265, 266, D_{10 \times 10}, 389, 390, \dots, 409, 410\}; & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 4062 \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{241, 242, \dots, 265, 266, D_{12 \times 12}, 411, 425, \dots, 435, 436\}; & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 4739 \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{211, 212, \dots, 239, 240, D_{14 \times 14}, 437, 438, \dots, 465, 466\}; & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 5416 \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{177, 178, \dots, 209, 210, D_{16 \times 16}, 467, 468, \dots, 499, 500\}; & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 6093
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{139, 140, \dots, 175, 176, D_{18 \times 18}, 501, 502, \dots, 537, 538\}; & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 6770 \\
 D_{22 \times 22} &:= \{97, 98, \dots, 137, 138, D_{20 \times 20}, 539, 540, \dots, 581, 580\}; & S_{22 \times 22} &:= 7447 \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{51, 52, \dots, 95, 96, D_{22 \times 22}, 581, 582, \dots, 625, 626\}; & S_{24 \times 24} &:= 8124 \\
 D_{26 \times 26} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 45, 46, D_{24 \times 24}, 627, 628, \dots, 675, 676\}; & S_{26 \times 26} &:= 8801.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are four different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 26. These four ways are based on the magic squares of orders 24 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.18, 3.20, 3.21 and 3.22.

2.9.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 576 by 69 to 644 in Example 3.18 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{24 \times 24}$ appearing in Example 2.9, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 given by

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	170	144	193	435	413	460	374	396	349	87	113	64	297	275	322	596	570	619	525	551	502	224	246	199	638
637	192	169	146	461	436	411	348	373	398	65	88	111	323	298	273	618	595	572	503	526	549	198	223	248	40
41	145	194	168	412	459	437	397	350	372	112	63	89	274	321	299	571	620	594	550	501	527	247	200	222	636
635	296	270	319	597	575	622	524	546	499	225	251	202	159	137	184	446	420	469	363	389	340	98	120	73	42
43	318	295	272	623	598	573	498	523	548	203	226	249	185	160	135	468	445	422	341	364	387	72	97	122	634
633	271	320	294	574	621	599	547	500	522	250	201	227	136	183	161	421	470	444	388	339	365	121	74	96	44
45	75	101	52	386	408	361	447	425	472	158	132	181	236	258	211	513	539	490	584	558	607	309	287	334	632
631	53	76	99	360	385	410	473	448	423	180	157	134	210	235	260	491	514	537	606	583	560	335	310	285	46
47	100	51	77	409	362	384	424	471	449	133	182	156	259	212	234	538	489	515	559	608	582	286	333	311	630
629	237	263	214	512	534	487	585	563	610	308	282	331	86	108	61	375	401	352	458	432	481	147	125	172	48
49	215	238	261	486	511	536	611	586	561	330	307	284	60	85	110	353	376	399	480	457	434	173	148	123	628
627	262	213	239	535	488	510	562	609	587	283	332	306	109	62	84	400	351	377	433	482	456	124	171	149	50
639	380	402	355	81	107	58	152	126	175	453	431	478	507	533	484	242	264	217	303	281	328	590	564	613	38
665	354	379	404	59	82	105	174	151	128	479	454	429	485	508	531	216	241	266	329	304	279	612	589	566	12
11	403	356	378	106	57	83	127	176	150	430	477	455	532	483	509	265	218	240	280	327	305	565	614	588	666
667	518	540	493	231	257	208	314	288	337	579	557	604	381	407	358	80	102	55	153	131	178	452	426	475	10
9	492	517	542	209	232	255	336	313	290	605	580	555	359	382	405	54	79	104	179	154	129	474	451	428	668
669	541	494	516	256	207	233	289	338	312	556	603	581	406	357	383	103	56	78	130	177	155	427	476	450	8
7	441	419	466	164	138	187	93	119	70	368	390	343	602	576	625	291	269	316	230	252	205	519	545	496	670
671	467	442	417	186	163	140	71	94	117	342	367	392	624	601	578	317	292	267	204	229	254	497	520	543	6
5	418	465	443	139	188	162	118	69	95	391	344	366	577	626	600	268	315	293	253	206	228	544	495	521	672
673	591	569	616	302	276	325	219	245	196	530	552	505	440	414	463	165	143	190	92	114	67	369	395	346	4
3	617	592	567	324	301	278	197	220	243	504	529	554	462	439	416	191	166	141	66	91	116	347	370	393	674
675	568	615	593	277	326	300	244	195	221	553	506	528	415	464	438	142	189	167	115	68	90	394	345	371	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26, where the magic square of order 24 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 8801 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 8124.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **magic squares** with **different magic sums**. Moreover, **pandiagonal magic square** of order 24 is also a **semi-bimagic square** with **semi-bimagic sum** $Sb_{24 \times 24} := 3413524$

2.9.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 576 by 69 to 644 in Example 3.20 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{24 \times 24}$ appearing in Example 2.9, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 given by

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	267	482	51	554	268	481	52	553	269	480	53	552	270	479	54	551	271	478	55	550	272	477	56	549	638
637	122	483	338	411	121	484	337	412	120	485	336	413	119	486	335	414	118	487	334	415	117	488	333	416	40
41	626	123	410	195	625	124	409	196	624	125	408	197	623	126	407	198	622	127	406	199	621	128	405	200	636
635	339	266	555	194	340	265	556	193	341	264	557	192	342	263	558	191	343	262	559	190	344	261	560	189	42
43	273	476	57	548	274	475	58	547	275	474	59	546	276	473	60	545	277	472	61	544	278	471	62	543	634
633	116	489	332	417	115	490	331	418	114	491	330	419	113	492	329	420	112	493	328	421	111	494	327	422	44
45	620	129	404	201	619	130	403	202	618	131	402	203	617	132	401	204	616	133	400	205	615	134	399	206	632
631	345	260	561	188	346	259	562	187	347	258	563	186	348	257	564	185	349	256	565	184	350	255	566	183	46
47	279	470	63	542	280	469	64	541	281	468	65	540	282	467	66	539	283	466	67	538	284	465	68	537	630
629	110	495	326	423	109	496	325	424	108	497	324	425	107	498	323	426	106	499	322	427	105	500	321	428	48
49	614	135	398	207	613	136	397	208	612	137	396	209	611	138	395	210	610	139	394	211	609	140	393	212	628
627	351	254	567	182	352	253	568	181	353	252	569	180	354	251	570	179	355	250	571	178	356	249	572	177	50
639	285	464	69	536	286	463	70	535	287	462	71	534	288	461	72	533	289	460	73	532	290	459	74	531	38
665	104	501	320	429	103	502	319	430	102	503	318	431	101	504	317	432	100	505	316	433	99	506	315	434	12
11	608	141	392	213	607	142	391	214	606	143	390	215	605	144	389	216	604	145	388	217	603	146	387	218	666
667	357	248	573	176	358	247	574	175	359	246	575	174	360	245	576	173	361	244	577	172	362	243	578	171	10
9	291	458	75	530	292	457	76	529	293	456	77	528	294	455	78	527	295	454	79	526	296	453	80	525	668
669	98	507	314	435	97	508	313	436	96	509	312	437	95	510	311	438	94	511	310	439	93	512	309	440	8
7	602	147	386	219	601	148	385	220	600	149	384	221	599	150	383	222	598	151	382	223	597	152	381	224	670
671	363	242	579	170	364	241	580	169	365	240	581	168	366	239	582	167	367	238	583	166	368	237	584	165	6
5	297	452	81	524	298	451	82	523	299	450	83	522	300	449	84	521	301	448	85	520	302	447	86	519	672
673	92	513	308	441	91	514	307	442	90	515	306	443	89	516	305	444	88	517	304	445	87	518	303	446	4
3	596	153	380	225	595	154	379	226	594	155	378	227	593	156	377	228	592	157	376	229	591	158	375	230	674
675	369	236	585	164	370	235	586	163	371	234	587	162	372	233	588	161	373	232	589	160	374	231	590	159	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26, where the magic square of order 24 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 8801, \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 8124 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 1354.$$

Blocks of order 4 are **pandigonal magic squares with equal magic sums**.

2.9.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 576 by 69 to 644 in Example 3.21 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{24 \times 24}$ appearing in Example 2.9, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 given by

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	51	595	594	563	82	146	52	596	593	564	81	145	53	597	592	565	80	144	54	598	591	566	79	143	638
637	530	178	498	179	211	435	529	177	497	180	212	436	528	176	496	181	213	437	527	175	495	182	214	438	40
41	434	403	275	306	370	243	433	404	276	305	369	244	432	405	277	304	368	245	431	406	278	303	367	246	636
635	338	274	371	402	307	339	337	273	372	401	308	340	336	272	373	400	309	341	335	271	374	399	310	342	42
43	147	466	210	467	499	242	148	465	209	468	500	241	149	464	208	469	501	240	150	463	207	470	502	239	634
633	531	115	83	114	562	626	532	116	84	113	561	625	533	117	85	112	560	624	534	118	86	111	559	623	44
45	55	599	590	567	78	142	56	600	589	568	77	141	57	601	588	569	76	140	58	602	587	570	75	139	632
631	526	174	494	183	215	439	525	173	493	184	216	440	524	172	492	185	217	441	523	171	491	186	218	442	46
47	430	407	279	302	366	247	429	408	280	301	365	248	428	409	281	300	364	249	427	410	282	299	363	250	630
629	334	270	375	398	311	343	333	269	376	397	312	344	332	268	377	396	313	345	331	267	378	395	314	346	48
49	151	462	206	471	503	238	152	461	205	472	504	237	153	460	204	473	505	236	154	459	203	474	506	235	628
627	535	119	87	110	558	622	536	120	88	109	557	621	537	121	89	108	556	620	538	122	90	107	555	619	50
639	59	603	586	571	74	138	60	604	585	572	73	137	61	605	584	573	72	136	62	606	583	574	71	135	38
665	522	170	490	187	219	443	521	169	489	188	220	444	520	168	488	189	221	445	519	167	487	190	222	446	12
11	426	411	283	298	362	251	425	412	284	297	361	252	424	413	285	296	360	253	423	414	286	295	359	254	666
667	330	266	379	394	315	347	329	265	380	393	316	348	328	264	381	392	317	349	327	263	382	391	318	350	10
9	155	458	202	475	507	234	156	457	201	476	508	233	157	456	200	477	509	232	158	455	199	478	510	231	668
669	539	123	91	106	554	618	540	124	92	105	553	617	541	125	93	104	552	616	542	126	94	103	551	615	8
7	63	607	582	575	70	134	64	608	581	576	69	133	65	609	580	577	68	132	66	610	579	578	67	131	670
671	518	166	486	191	223	447	517	165	485	192	224	448	516	164	484	193	225	449	515	163	483	194	226	450	6
5	422	415	287	294	358	255	421	416	288	293	357	256	420	417	289	292	356	257	419	418	290	291	355	258	672
673	326	262	383	390	319	351	325	261	384	389	320	352	324	260	385	388	321	353	323	259	386	387	322	354	4
3	159	454	198	479	511	230	160	453	197	480	512	229	161	452	196	481	513	228	162	451	195	482	514	227	674
675	543	127	95	102	550	614	544	128	96	101	549	613	545	129	97	100	548	612	546	130	98	99	547	611	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 with following sums:

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 8801, \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 8124 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 2031.$$

Blocks of order 6 are **magic squares with equal magic sums**.

2.9.4 Forth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 576 by 69 to 644 in Example 3.22 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{24 \times 24}$ appearing in Example 2.9, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 given by

25	663	15	661	17	659	19	657	21	655	23	653	1	664	27	649	29	647	31	645	33	643	35	641	37	651
39	193	460	349	64	322	619	502	199	144	413	396	113	275	570	551	246	170	435	374	87	297	596	525	224	638
637	319	622	499	202	184	469	340	73	270	575	546	251	137	420	389	120	296	597	524	225	159	446	363	98	40
41	52	361	472	181	211	490	607	334	101	408	425	132	258	539	558	287	75	386	447	158	236	513	584	309	636
635	214	487	610	331	61	352	481	172	263	534	563	282	108	401	432	125	237	512	585	308	86	375	458	147	42
43	355	58	175	478	484	217	328	613	402	107	126	431	533	264	281	564	380	81	152	453	507	242	303	590	634
633	493	208	337	604	358	55	178	475	540	257	288	557	407	102	131	426	518	231	314	579	381	80	153	452	44
45	466	187	70	343	625	316	205	496	419	138	119	390	576	269	252	545	441	164	93	368	602	291	230	519	632
631	616	325	196	505	463	190	67	346	569	276	245	552	414	143	114	395	591	302	219	530	440	165	92	369	46
47	146	411	398	111	273	572	549	248	169	436	373	88	298	595	526	223	192	461	348	65	323	618	503	198	630
629	272	573	548	249	135	422	387	122	295	598	523	226	160	445	364	97	318	623	498	203	185	468	341	72	48
49	99	410	423	134	260	537	560	285	76	385	448	157	235	514	583	310	53	360	473	180	210	491	606	335	628
627	261	536	561	284	110	399	434	123	238	511	586	307	85	376	457	148	215	486	611	330	60	353	480	173	50
639	404	105	128	429	531	266	279	566	379	82	151	454	508	241	304	589	354	59	174	479	485	216	329	612	38
665	542	255	290	555	405	104	129	428	517	232	313	580	382	79	154	451	492	209	336	605	359	54	179	474	12
11	417	140	117	392	578	267	254	543	442	163	94	367	601	292	229	520	467	186	71	342	624	317	204	497	666
667	567	278	243	554	416	141	116	393	592	301	220	529	439	166	91	370	617	324	197	504	462	191	66	347	10
9	168	437	372	89	299	594	527	222	194	459	350	63	321	620	501	200	145	412	397	112	274	571	550	247	668
669	294	599	522	227	161	444	365	96	320	621	500	201	183	470	339	74	271	574	547	250	136	421	388	121	8
7	77	384	449	156	234	515	582	311	51	362	471	182	212	489	608	333	100	409	424	133	259	538	559	286	670
671	239	510	587	306	84	377	456	149	213	488	609	332	62	351	482	171	262	535	562	283	109	400	433	124	6
5	378	83	150	455	509	240	305	588	356	57	176	477	483	218	327	614	403	106	127	430	532	265	280	565	672
673	516	233	312	581	383	78	155	450	494	207	338	603	357	56	177	476	541	256	289	556	406	103	130	427	4
3	443	162	95	366	600	293	228	521	465	188	69	344	626	315	206	495	418	139	118	391	577	268	253	544	674
675	593	300	221	528	438	167	90	371	615	326	195	506	464	189	68	345	568	277	244	553	415	142	115	394	2
26	14	662	16	660	18	658	20	656	22	654	24	676	13	650	28	648	30	646	32	644	34	642	36	640	652

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 26, where the magic square of order 24 is **semi-bimagic** with following sums:

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 8801, \quad S_{24 \times 24} := 8124 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{8 \times 8} := 2708.$$

Blocks of order 8 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with equal magic sums. Moreover, each **pandiagonal magic square** of order 8 is either **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** with **different magic** or **semi-bimagic** sums resulting in a **semi-bimagic square** of order 24 with **semi-bimagic sum** as $Sb_{24 \times 24} := 3413524$.

Summarizing, we have following result

Result 2.9. *We have written block-bordered magic square of order 26 in four different ways. The blocks are considered as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 24, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums. These blocks of order 3 results in a semi-bimagic square of order 24.*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 24, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- (iii) *Magic square of 24, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- (iv) *Pandiagonal magic square of 24, where block of order 8 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums. Moreover, blocks of order 8 are either bimagic squares or semi-bimagic squares with different bimagic or semi-bimagic sums. These blocks of order 8 results in a semi-bimagic square of order 24.*

2.10 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 29

Example 2.10. *Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 29 given by*

814	786	788	790	792	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	27	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	812
55	760	107	105	103	101	99	97	95	93	91	89	87	85	83	763	765	767	769	771	773	775	777	779	781	783	785	84	787
53	734	710	686	688	690	692	694	696	698	700	702	704	706	131	130	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	112	110	708	108	789
51	736	155	180	200	198	196	194	192	190	188	186	184	182	665	666	668	670	672	674	676	678	680	682	684	178	687	106	791
49	738	153	685	620	202	204	206	208	210	212	214	216	218	219	618	616	614	612	610	608	606	604	602	622	157	689	104	793
47	740	151	683	603	584	566	568	570	572	574	576	578	580	257	256	254	252	250	248	246	244	242	582	239	159	691	102	795
45	742	149	681	605	275	292	564	562	560	558	556	554	552	551	296	298	300	302	304	306	308	294	567	237	161	693	100	797
43	744	147	679	607	273	277	322	532	530	528	526	524	522	521	326	328	330	332	334	336	324	565	569	235	163	695	98	799
41	746	145	677	609	271	279	309	350	360	358	356	354	352	495	496	498	500	502	504	348	533	563	571	233	165	697	96	801
39	748	143	675	611	269	281	311	505	472	379	377	375	373	371	475	477	479	481	372	337	531	561	573	231	167	699	94	803
37	750	141	673	613	267	283	313	503	462	452	382	384	386	387	450	448	446	454	380	339	529	559	575	229	169	701	92	805
35	752	139	671	615	265	285	315	501	464	447	404	408	406	441	442	444	402	395	378	341	527	557	577	227	171	703	90	807
33	754	137	669	617	263	287	317	499	466	449	445	428	427	429	409	412	397	393	376	343	525	555	579	225	173	705	88	809
31	756	135	667	619	261	289	319	497	468	451	443	410	422	417	424	432	399	391	374	345	523	553	581	223	175	707	86	811
29	81	133	179	621	259	549	519	349	369	453	403	411	423	421	419	431	439	389	473	493	323	293	583	221	663	709	761	813
817	80	713	181	217	587	547	517	351	368	385	405	426	418	425	420	416	437	457	474	491	325	295	255	625	661	129	762	25
819	78	715	183	215	589	545	515	353	366	383	407	430	415	413	433	414	435	459	476	489	327	297	253	627	659	127	764	23
821	76	717	185	213	591	543	513	355	364	381	440	434	436	401	400	398	438	461	478	487	329	299	251	629	657	125	766	21
823	74	719	187	211	593	541	511	357	362	388	460	458	456	455	392	394	396	390	480	485	331	301	249	631	655	123	768	19
825	72	721	189	209	595	539	509	359	470	463	465	467	469	471	367	365	363	361	370	483	333	303	247	633	653	121	770	17
827	70	723	191	207	597	537	507	494	482	484	486	488	490	347	346	344	342	340	338	492	335	305	245	635	651	119	772	15
829	68	725	193	205	599	535	518	310	312	314	316	318	320	321	516	514	512	510	508	506	520	307	243	637	649	117	774	13
831	66	727	195	203	601	548	278	280	282	284	286	288	290	291	546	544	542	540	538	536	534	550	241	639	647	115	776	11
833	64	729	197	201	260	276	274	272	270	268	266	264	262	585	586	588	590	592	594	596	598	600	258	641	645	113	778	9
835	62	731	199	220	640	638	636	634	632	630	628	626	624	623	224	226	228	230	232	234	236	238	240	222	643	111	780	7
837	60	733	664	642	644	646	648	650	652	654	656	658	660	177	176	174	172	170	168	166	164	162	160	158	662	109	782	5
839	58	134	156	154	152	150	148	146	144	142	140	138	136	711	712	714	716	718	720	722	724	726	728	730	732	132	784	3
841	758	735	737	739	741	743	745	747	749	751	753	755	757	759	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	65	63	61	59	57	82	1
30	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	815	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	28

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{417, 418, 419, 420, 421, 422, 423, 424, 425\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 1263 \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{409, 410, \dots, 415, 416, D_{3 \times 3}, 426, 427, \dots, 432, 433\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 2105 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{397, 398, \dots, 407, 408, D_{5 \times 5}, 434, 435, \dots, 444, 445\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 2947 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{381, 382, \dots, 395, 396, D_{7 \times 7}, 446, 447, \dots, 460, 461\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 3789 \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{361, 362, \dots, 379, 380, D_{9 \times 9}, 462, 463, \dots, 480, 481\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 4631 \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{337, 338, \dots, 359, 360, D_{11 \times 11}, 482, 483, \dots, 504, 505\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 5473 \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{309, 310, \dots, 335, 336, D_{13 \times 13}, 506, 507, \dots, 532, 533\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 6315 \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{277, 278, \dots, 307, 308, D_{15 \times 15}, 534, 535, \dots, 564, 565\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 7157
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{241, 242, \dots, 275, 276, D_{17 \times 17}, 566, 567, \dots, 600, 601\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 7999 \\ D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{201, 202, \dots, 239, 240, D_{19 \times 19}, 602, 603, \dots, 640, 641\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 8841 \\ D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{157, 158, \dots, 199, 200, D_{21 \times 21}, 642, 643, \dots, 684, 685\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 9683 \\ D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{109, 110, \dots, 155, 156, D_{23 \times 23}, 686, 687, \dots, 732, 733\}; & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 10525 \\ D_{27 \times 27} &:= \{57, 58, \dots, 107, 108, D_{25 \times 25}, 774, 775, \dots, 732, 785\}; & S_{27 \times 27} &:= 11367 \\ D_{29 \times 29} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 55, 56, D_{27 \times 27}, 786, 787, \dots, 840, 841\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 12209. \end{aligned}$$

Below are three different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 29. These two ways are based on the magic squares of orders 27 and 25 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.24, 3.25 and 3.23.

2.10.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 729 by 57 to 785 in Example 3.24 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{27 \times 27}$ appearing in Example 2.10, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 given by

814	786	788	790	792	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	27	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	812
55	678	505	80	692	490	81	682	507	74	693	494	76	698	495	70	699	500	64	686	511	66	703	501	59	688	515	60	787
53	73	701	489	58	702	503	75	695	493	62	697	504	63	691	509	68	685	510	79	687	497	69	680	514	83	681	499	789
51	512	57	694	513	71	679	506	61	696	508	72	683	502	77	684	496	78	689	498	65	700	491	82	690	492	67	704	791
49	705	100	458	719	85	459	709	102	452	720	89	454	725	90	448	726	95	442	713	106	444	730	96	437	715	110	438	793
47	451	728	84	436	729	98	453	722	88	440	724	99	441	718	104	446	712	105	457	714	92	447	707	109	461	708	94	795
45	107	435	721	108	449	706	101	439	723	103	450	710	97	455	711	91	456	716	93	443	727	86	460	717	87	445	731	797
43	516	559	188	530	544	189	520	561	182	531	548	184	536	549	178	537	554	172	524	565	174	541	555	167	526	569	168	799
41	181	539	543	166	540	557	183	533	547	170	535	558	171	529	563	176	523	564	187	525	551	177	518	568	191	519	553	801
39	566	165	532	567	179	517	560	169	534	562	180	521	556	185	522	550	186	527	552	173	538	545	190	528	546	175	542	803
37	570	208	485	584	193	486	574	210	479	585	197	481	590	198	475	591	203	469	578	214	471	595	204	464	580	218	465	805
35	478	593	192	463	594	206	480	587	196	467	589	207	468	583	212	473	577	213	484	579	200	474	572	217	488	573	202	807
33	215	462	586	216	476	571	209	466	588	211	477	575	205	482	576	199	483	581	201	470	592	194	487	582	195	472	596	809
31	408	235	620	422	220	621	412	237	614	423	224	616	428	225	610	429	230	604	416	241	606	433	231	599	418	245	600	811
29	613	431	219	598	432	233	615	425	223	602	427	234	603	421	239	608	415	240	619	417	227	609	410	244	623	411	229	813
817	242	597	424	243	611	409	236	601	426	238	612	413	232	617	414	226	618	419	228	605	430	221	622	420	222	607	434	25
819	246	370	647	260	355	648	250	372	641	261	359	643	266	360	637	267	365	631	254	376	633	271	366	626	256	380	627	23
821	640	269	354	625	270	368	642	263	358	629	265	369	630	259	374	635	253	375	646	255	362	636	248	379	650	249	364	21
823	377	624	262	378	638	247	371	628	264	373	639	251	367	644	252	361	645	257	363	632	268	356	649	258	357	634	272	19
825	300	667	296	314	652	297	304	669	290	315	656	292	320	657	286	321	662	280	308	673	282	325	663	275	310	677	276	17
827	289	323	651	274	324	665	291	317	655	278	319	666	279	313	671	284	307	672	295	309	659	285	302	676	299	303	661	15
829	674	273	316	675	287	301	668	277	318	670	288	305	664	293	306	658	294	311	660	281	322	653	298	312	654	283	326	13
831	111	397	755	125	382	756	115	399	749	126	386	751	131	387	745	132	392	739	119	403	741	136	393	734	121	407	735	11
833	748	134	381	733	135	395	750	128	385	737	130	396	738	124	401	743	118	402	754	120	389	744	113	406	758	114	391	9
835	404	732	127	405	746	112	398	736	129	400	747	116	394	752	117	388	753	122	390	740	133	383	757	123	384	742	137	7
837	138	775	350	152	760	351	142	777	344	153	764	346	158	765	340	159	770	334	146	781	336	163	771	329	148	785	330	5
839	343	161	759	328	162	773	345	155	763	332	157	774	333	151	779	338	145	780	349	147	767	339	140	784	353	141	769	3
841	782	327	154	783	341	139	776	331	156	778	342	143	772	347	144	766	348	149	768	335	160	761	352	150	762	337	164	1
30	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	815	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	28

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29, where the magic square of order 27 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{29 \times 29} := 12209, \quad S_{27 \times 27} := 11367 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 1293.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.10.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 729 by 57 to 785 in Example 3.25 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{27 \times 27}$ appearing in Example 2.10, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 given by

814	786	788	790	792	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	27	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	812
55	760	107	105	103	101	99	97	95	93	91	89	87	85	83	763	765	767	769	771	773	775	777	779	781	783	785	84	787
53	734	109	277	415	583	721	551	689	232	245	388	343	381	519	662	200	655	173	311	474	492	447	585	628	141	304	108	789
51	736	565	733	121	259	427	257	395	538	701	214	669	187	350	368	531	461	499	642	180	323	153	291	454	597	610	106	791
49	738	271	409	577	715	133	688	226	239	407	545	375	518	681	194	337	167	330	473	486	649	604	622	135	303	441	104	793
47	740	727	115	283	421	559	389	557	695	213	251	206	344	362	525	668	498	636	174	317	480	285	453	591	629	147	102	795
45	742	433	571	709	127	265	220	238	401	539	707	512	675	193	356	369	324	467	505	648	161	616	154	297	435	603	100	797
43	744	643	181	319	462	500	455	598	611	149	292	122	260	428	566	729	534	702	215	258	396	351	364	532	670	188	98	799
41	746	469	487	650	168	331	136	299	442	605	623	578	716	129	272	410	240	408	546	684	227	682	195	338	376	514	96	801
39	748	175	318	481	494	637	592	630	148	286	449	279	422	560	728	116	696	209	252	390	558	363	526	664	207	345	94	803
37	750	506	644	162	325	468	298	436	599	617	155	710	128	266	429	572	402	540	708	221	234	189	357	370	513	676	92	805
35	752	312	475	493	656	169	624	142	305	448	586	416	579	722	110	278	233	246	384	552	690	520	663	201	339	382	90	807
33	754	547	685	228	241	404	334	377	515	683	196	651	164	332	470	488	443	606	619	137	300	130	273	411	574	717	88	809
31	756	253	391	554	697	210	665	208	346	359	527	482	495	638	176	314	144	287	450	593	631	561	724	117	280	423	86	811
29	81	704	222	235	403	541	371	509	677	190	358	163	326	464	507	645	600	618	156	294	437	267	430	573	711	124	761	813
817	80	385	553	691	229	247	202	340	383	521	659	489	657	170	313	476	306	444	587	625	143	723	111	274	417	580	762	25
819	78	216	254	397	535	703	533	671	184	352	365	320	463	501	639	182	612	150	293	456	594	424	567	730	123	261	764	23
821	76	451	589	632	145	288	118	281	419	562	725	555	698	211	249	392	347	360	528	666	204	634	177	315	483	496	766	21
823	74	157	295	438	601	614	569	712	125	268	431	236	399	542	705	223	678	191	354	372	510	465	508	646	159	327	768	19
825	72	588	626	139	307	445	275	418	581	719	112	692	230	248	386	549	379	522	660	203	341	171	309	477	490	658	770	17
827	70	289	457	595	613	151	731	119	262	425	568	398	536	699	217	255	185	353	366	529	672	502	640	183	321	459	772	15
829	68	620	138	301	439	607	412	575	718	131	269	224	242	405	548	686	516	679	197	335	378	333	471	484	652	165	774	13
831	66	355	373	511	674	192	647	160	328	466	504	434	602	615	158	296	126	264	432	570	713	543	706	219	237	400	776	11
833	64	661	199	342	380	523	478	491	654	172	310	140	308	446	584	627	582	720	113	276	414	244	387	550	693	231	778	9
835	62	367	530	673	186	349	179	322	460	503	641	596	609	152	290	458	263	426	564	732	120	700	218	256	394	537	780	7
837	60	198	336	374	517	680	485	653	166	329	472	302	440	608	621	134	714	132	270	413	576	406	544	687	225	243	782	5
839	58	524	667	205	348	361	316	479	497	635	178	633	146	284	452	590	420	563	726	114	282	212	250	393	556	694	784	3
841	758	735	737	739	741	743	745	747	749	751	753	755	757	759	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	65	63	61	59	57	82	1
30	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	815	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	28

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29, where the magic square of order 27 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{29 \times 29} := 12209, \quad S_{27 \times 27} := 11367 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 3789.$$

Blocks of order 9 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**. Also the sum of 9 members of each block of order 3 are the same as of magic square of order 9.

2.10.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 625 by 109 to 733 in Example 3.23 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{25 \times 25}$ appearing in Example 2.10, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 given by

814	786	788	790	792	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	27	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	812
55	760	107	105	103	101	99	97	95	93	91	89	87	85	83	763	765	767	769	771	773	775	777	779	781	783	785	84	787
53	734	109	277	415	583	721	551	689	232	245	388	343	381	519	662	200	655	173	311	474	492	447	585	628	141	304	108	789
51	736	565	733	121	259	427	257	395	538	701	214	669	187	350	368	531	461	499	642	180	323	153	291	454	597	610	106	791
49	738	271	409	577	715	133	688	226	239	407	545	375	518	681	194	337	167	330	473	486	649	604	622	135	303	441	104	793
47	740	727	115	283	421	559	389	557	695	213	251	206	344	362	525	668	498	636	174	317	480	285	453	591	629	147	102	795
45	742	433	571	709	127	265	220	238	401	539	707	512	675	193	356	369	324	467	505	648	161	616	154	297	435	603	100	797
43	744	643	181	319	462	500	455	598	611	149	292	122	260	428	566	729	534	702	215	258	396	351	364	532	670	188	98	799
41	746	469	487	650	168	331	136	299	442	605	623	578	716	129	272	410	240	408	546	684	227	682	195	338	376	514	96	801
39	748	175	318	481	494	637	592	630	148	286	449	279	422	560	728	116	696	209	252	390	558	363	526	664	207	345	94	803
37	750	506	644	162	325	468	298	436	599	617	155	710	128	266	429	572	402	540	708	221	234	189	357	370	513	676	92	805
35	752	312	475	493	656	169	624	142	305	448	586	416	579	722	110	278	233	246	384	552	690	520	663	201	339	382	90	807
33	754	547	685	228	241	404	334	377	515	683	196	651	164	332	470	488	443	606	619	137	300	130	273	411	574	717	88	809
31	756	253	391	554	697	210	665	208	346	359	527	482	495	638	176	314	144	287	450	593	631	561	724	117	280	423	86	811
29	81	704	222	235	403	541	371	509	677	190	358	163	326	464	507	645	600	618	156	294	437	267	430	573	711	124	761	813
817	80	385	553	691	229	247	202	340	383	521	659	489	657	170	313	476	306	444	587	625	143	723	111	274	417	580	762	25
819	78	216	254	397	535	703	533	671	184	352	365	320	463	501	639	182	612	150	293	456	594	424	567	730	123	261	764	23
821	76	451	589	632	145	288	118	281	419	562	725	555	698	211	249	392	347	360	528	666	204	634	177	315	483	496	766	21
823	74	157	295	438	601	614	569	712	125	268	431	236	399	542	705	223	678	191	354	372	510	465	508	646	159	327	768	19
825	72	588	626	139	307	445	275	418	581	719	112	692	230	248	386	549	379	522	660	203	341	171	309	477	490	658	770	17
827	70	289	457	595	613	151	731	119	262	425	568	398	536	699	217	255	185	353	366	529	672	502	640	183	321	459	772	15
829	68	620	138	301	439	607	412	575	718	131	269	224	242	405	548	686	516	679	197	335	378	333	471	484	652	165	774	13
831	66	355	373	511	674	192	647	160	328	466	504	434	602	615	158	296	126	264	432	570	713	543	706	219	237	400	776	11
833	64	661	199	342	380	523	478	491	654	172	310	140	308	446	584	627	582	720	113	276	414	244	387	550	693	231	778	9
835	62	367	530	673	186	349	179	322	460	503	641	596	609	152	290	458	263	426	564	732	120	700	218	256	394	537	780	7
837	60	198	336	374	517	680	485	653	166	329	472	302	440	608	621	134	714	132	270	413	576	406	544	687	225	243	782	5
839	58	524	667	205	348	361	316	479	497	635	178	633	146	284	452	590	420	563	726	114	282	212	250	393	556	694	784	3
841	758	735	737	739	741	743	745	747	749	751	753	755	757	759	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	65	63	61	59	57	82	1
30	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	815	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	28

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 29, where the magic square of order 25 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** with following sums:

$$S_{29 \times 29} := 12209, \quad S_{27 \times 27} := 11367, \quad S_{25 \times 25} := 10525 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 2105.$$

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**. Moreover, the magic square of order 25 is **pandiagonal bimagic square** with **bimagic sum** $Sb_{25 \times 25} := 5244825$.

Summarizing, we have following result

Result 2.10. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 in two three ways. The blocks are considered as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 27, where blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares with equal semi-magic sums**;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 27, where blocks of order 9 are **pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums**;*
- (iii) *Pandiagonal bimagic square of 25, where blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums**.*

2.11 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 31

Example 2.11. *Let's consider a **bordered magic square of order 31** given by*

932	902	904	906	908	910	912	914	916	918	920	922	924	926	928	29	28	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	930
59	88	61	63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	873	871	869	867	865	863	861	859	857	855	853	851	849	847	872	903
57	900	820	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	812	814	816	141	140	138	136	134	132	130	128	126	124	122	120	118	818	62	905
55	898	167	768	747	749	751	753	755	757	759	761	763	765	767	769	189	187	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	171	169	192	795	64	907
53	896	165	170	238	744	742	740	738	736	734	732	730	728	726	725	242	244	246	248	250	252	254	256	258	260	240	792	797	66	909
51	894	163	172	217	280	700	698	696	694	692	690	688	686	684	683	284	286	288	290	292	294	296	298	300	282	745	790	799	68	911
49	892	161	174	219	261	642	627	629	631	633	635	637	639	641	643	315	313	311	309	307	305	303	301	318	701	743	788	801	70	913
47	890	159	176	221	263	302	354	368	366	364	362	360	358	356	611	612	614	616	618	620	622	624	352	660	699	741	786	803	72	915
45	888	157	178	223	265	304	625	384	593	591	589	587	585	583	383	385	387	389	391	393	395	580	337	658	697	739	784	805	74	917
43	886	155	180	225	267	306	623	396	410	565	563	561	559	557	409	411	413	415	417	419	554	566	339	656	695	737	782	807	76	919
41	884	153	182	227	269	308	621	394	420	532	439	437	435	433	431	535	537	539	541	432	542	568	341	654	693	735	780	809	78	921
39	882	151	184	229	271	310	619	392	418	522	448	520	518	516	515	452	454	456	450	440	544	570	343	652	691	733	778	811	80	923
37	880	149	186	231	273	312	617	390	416	524	441	464	468	466	501	502	504	462	521	438	546	572	345	650	689	731	776	813	82	925
35	878	147	188	233	275	314	615	388	414	526	443	505	472	492	491	476	474	457	519	436	548	574	347	648	687	729	774	815	84	927
33	876	145	190	235	277	316	613	386	412	528	445	503	469	480	485	478	493	459	517	434	550	576	349	646	685	727	772	817	86	929
31	875	143	191	723	681	317	353	581	555	429	513	463	489	479	481	483	473	499	449	533	407	381	609	645	281	239	771	819	87	931
935	92	823	766	721	679	640	355	582	556	428	511	465	487	484	477	482	475	497	451	534	406	380	607	322	283	241	196	139	870	27
937	94	825	764	719	677	638	357	584	558	426	509	467	488	470	471	486	490	495	453	536	404	378	605	324	285	243	198	137	868	25
939	96	827	762	717	675	636	359	586	560	424	507	500	494	496	461	460	458	498	455	538	402	376	603	326	287	245	200	135	866	23
941	98	829	760	715	673	634	361	588	562	422	512	442	444	446	447	510	508	506	514	540	400	374	601	328	289	247	202	133	864	21
943	100	831	758	713	671	632	363	590	564	530	523	525	527	529	531	427	425	423	421	430	398	372	599	330	291	249	204	131	862	19
945	102	833	756	711	669	630	365	592	408	397	399	401	403	405	553	551	549	547	545	543	552	370	597	332	293	251	206	129	860	17
947	104	835	754	709	667	628	367	382	369	371	373	375	377	379	579	577	575	573	571	569	567	578	595	334	295	253	208	127	858	15
949	106	837	752	707	665	626	610	594	596	598	600	602	604	606	351	350	348	346	344	342	340	338	608	336	297	255	210	125	856	13
951	108	839	750	705	663	644	335	333	331	329	327	325	323	321	319	647	649	651	653	655	657	659	661	320	299	257	212	123	854	11
953	110	841	748	703	680	262	264	266	268	270	272	274	276	278	279	678	676	674	672	670	668	666	664	662	682	259	214	121	852	9
955	112	843	746	722	218	220	222	224	226	228	230	232	234	236	237	720	718	716	714	712	710	708	706	704	702	724	216	119	850	7
957	114	845	770	215	213	211	209	207	205	203	201	199	197	195	193	773	775	777	779	781	783	785	787	789	791	793	194	117	848	5
959	116	144	168	166	164	162	160	158	156	154	152	150	148	146	821	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	842	844	142	846	3
961	90	901	899	897	895	893	891	889	887	885	883	881	879	877	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	874	1
32	60	58	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	933	934	936	938	940	942	944	946	948	950	952	954	956	958	960	30

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic square sums:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{3 \times 3} &:= \{477, 478, 479, 480, 481, 482, 483, 484, 485\}; & S_{3 \times 3} &:= 1443 \\
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{469, 470, \dots, 475, 476, D_{3 \times 3}, 486, 487, \dots, 492, 493\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 2405 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{457, 458, \dots, 467, 468, D_{5 \times 5}, 494, 495, \dots, 504, 505\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 3367 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{441, 442, \dots, 455, 456, D_{7 \times 7}, 506, 507, \dots, 520, 521\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 4329 \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{421, 422, \dots, 439, 440, D_{9 \times 9}, 522, 523, \dots, 540, 541\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 5291
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{397, 398, \dots, 419, 420, D_{11 \times 11}, 542, 543, \dots, 564, 565\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 6253 \\ D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{369, 370, \dots, 395, 396, D_{13 \times 13}, 566, 567, \dots, 592, 593\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 7215 \\ D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{337, 338, \dots, 367, 368, D_{15 \times 15}, 594, 595, \dots, 624, 625\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 8177 \\ D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{301, 302, \dots, 335, 336, D_{17 \times 17}, 626, 627, \dots, 660, 661\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 9139 \\ D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{261, 262, \dots, 299, 300, D_{19 \times 19}, 662, 663, \dots, 700, 701\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 10101 \\ D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{217, 218, \dots, 259, 260, D_{21 \times 21}, 702, 703, \dots, 744, 745\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 11063 \\ D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{169, 170, \dots, 215, 216, D_{23 \times 23}, 746, 747, \dots, 792, 793\}; & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 12025 \\ D_{27 \times 27} &:= \{117, 118, \dots, 167, 168, D_{25 \times 25}, 834, 835, \dots, 792, 845\}; & S_{27 \times 27} &:= 12997 \\ D_{29 \times 29} &:= \{61, 62, \dots, 115, 116, D_{27 \times 27}, 846, 847, \dots, 900, 901\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 13949 \\ D_{31 \times 31} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 59, 60, D_{27 \times 27}, 902, 903, \dots, 960, 961\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 14911. \end{aligned}$$

Below are three different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic squares of order 31. These two ways are based on the magic squares of orders 27 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.24 and 3.25.

2.11.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 729 by 117 to 845 in Example 3.24 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{27 \times 27}$ appearing in Example 2.11, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 given by

932	902	904	906	908	910	912	914	916	918	920	922	924	926	928	29	28	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	930
59	88	61	63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	873	871	869	867	865	863	861	859	857	855	853	851	849	847	872	903
57	900	117	739	551	133	755	564	140	759	571	126	748	560	142	764	573	122	741	553	135	757	569	124	746	555	131	750	562	62	905
55	898	251	789	439	228	769	419	235	776	423	233	771	421	237	778	428	244	785	432	242	780	430	246	787	437	226	767	414	64	907
53	896	346	644	453	353	648	460	339	637	449	355	653	462	335	630	442	348	646	458	337	635	444	344	639	451	357	655	467	66	909
51	894	468	280	659	484	296	672	491	300	679	477	289	668	493	305	681	473	282	661	486	298	677	475	287	663	482	291	670	68	911
49	892	602	168	709	579	148	689	586	155	693	584	150	691	588	157	698	595	164	702	593	159	700	597	166	707	577	146	684	70	913
47	890	373	266	804	380	270	811	366	259	800	382	275	813	362	252	793	375	268	809	364	257	795	371	261	802	384	277	818	72	915
45	888	819	388	200	835	404	213	842	408	220	828	397	209	844	413	222	824	390	202	837	406	218	826	395	204	833	399	211	74	917
43	886	629	519	331	606	499	311	613	506	315	611	501	313	615	508	320	622	515	324	620	510	322	624	517	329	604	497	306	76	919
41	884	724	536	183	731	540	190	717	529	179	733	545	192	713	522	172	726	538	188	715	527	174	722	531	181	735	547	197	78	921
39	882	441	334	632	457	350	645	464	354	652	450	343	641	466	359	654	446	336	634	459	352	650	448	341	636	455	345	643	80	923
37	880	575	141	763	552	121	743	559	128	747	557	123	745	561	130	752	568	137	756	566	132	754	570	139	761	550	119	738	82	925
35	878	427	239	777	434	243	784	420	232	773	436	248	786	416	225	766	429	241	782	418	230	768	425	234	775	438	250	791	84	927
33	876	792	361	254	808	377	267	815	381	274	801	370	263	817	386	276	797	363	256	810	379	272	799	368	258	806	372	265	86	929
31	875	683	492	304	660	472	284	667	479	288	665	474	286	669	481	293	676	488	297	674	483	295	678	490	302	658	470	279	87	931
935	92	697	590	156	704	594	163	690	583	152	706	599	165	686	576	145	699	592	161	688	581	147	695	585	154	708	601	170	870	27
937	94	171	712	524	187	728	537	194	732	544	180	721	533	196	737	546	176	714	526	189	730	542	178	719	528	185	723	535	868	25
939	96	224	843	412	201	823	392	208	830	396	206	825	394	210	832	401	217	839	405	215	834	403	219	841	410	199	821	387	866	23
941	98	319	617	507	326	621	514	312	610	503	328	626	516	308	603	496	321	619	512	310	608	498	317	612	505	330	628	521	864	21
943	100	765	415	227	781	431	240	788	435	247	774	424	236	790	440	249	770	417	229	783	433	245	772	422	231	779	426	238	862	19
945	102	656	465	358	633	445	338	640	452	342	638	447	340	642	454	347	649	461	351	647	456	349	651	463	356	631	443	333	860	17
947	104	751	563	129	758	567	136	744	556	125	760	572	138	740	549	118	753	565	134	742	554	120	749	558	127	762	574	143	858	15
949	106	144	685	578	160	701	591	167	705	598	153	694	587	169	710	600	149	687	580	162	703	596	151	692	582	158	696	589	856	13
951	108	278	816	385	255	796	365	262	803	369	260	798	367	264	805	374	271	812	378	269	807	376	273	814	383	253	794	360	854	11
953	110	292	671	480	299	675	487	285	664	476	301	680	489	281	657	469	294	673	485	283	662	471	290	666	478	303	682	494	852	9
955	112	495	307	605	511	323	618	518	327	625	504	316	614	520	332	627	500	309	607	513	325	623	502	314	609	509	318	616	850	7
957	114	548	195	736	525	175	716	532	182	720	530	177	718	534	184	725	541	191	729	539	186	727	543	193	734	523	173	711	848	5
959	116	400	212	831	407	216	838	393	205	827	409	221	840	389	198	820	402	214	836	391	203	822	398	207	829	411	223	845	846	3
961	90	901	899	897	895	893	891	889	887	885	883	881	879	877	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	874	1
32	60	58	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	933	934	936	938	940	942	944	946	948	950	952	954	956	958	960	30

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31, where the magic square of order 27 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{31 \times 31} := 14911, \quad S_{29 \times 29} := 13949, \quad S_{27 \times 27} := 12997 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 1433.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.11.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 729 by 117 to 845 in Example 3.25 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{27 \times 27}$ appearing in Example 2.11, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 given by

932	902	904	906	908	910	912	914	916	918	920	922	924	926	928	29	28	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	930
59	88	61	63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	873	871	869	867	865	863	861	859	857	855	853	851	849	847	872	903
57	900	738	565	140	752	550	141	742	567	134	753	554	136	758	555	130	759	560	124	746	571	126	763	561	119	748	575	120	62	905
55	898	133	761	549	118	762	563	135	755	553	122	757	564	123	751	569	128	745	570	139	747	557	129	740	574	143	741	559	64	907
53	896	572	117	754	573	131	739	566	121	756	568	132	743	562	137	744	556	138	749	558	125	760	551	142	750	552	127	764	66	909
51	894	765	160	518	779	145	519	769	162	512	780	149	514	785	150	508	786	155	502	773	166	504	790	156	497	775	170	498	68	911
49	892	511	788	144	496	789	158	513	782	148	500	784	159	501	778	164	506	772	165	517	774	152	507	767	169	521	768	154	70	913
47	890	167	495	781	168	509	766	161	499	783	163	510	770	157	515	771	151	516	776	153	503	787	146	520	777	147	505	791	72	915
45	888	576	619	248	590	604	249	580	621	242	591	608	244	596	609	238	597	614	232	584	625	234	601	615	227	586	629	228	74	917
43	886	241	599	603	226	600	617	243	593	607	230	595	618	231	589	623	236	583	624	247	585	611	237	578	628	251	579	613	76	919
41	884	626	225	592	627	239	577	620	229	594	622	240	581	616	245	582	610	246	587	612	233	598	605	250	588	606	235	602	78	921
39	882	630	268	545	644	253	546	634	270	539	645	257	541	650	258	535	651	263	529	638	274	531	655	264	524	640	278	525	80	923
37	880	538	653	252	523	654	266	540	647	256	527	649	267	528	643	272	533	637	273	544	639	260	534	632	277	548	633	262	82	925
35	878	275	522	646	276	536	631	269	526	648	271	537	635	265	542	636	259	543	641	261	530	652	254	547	642	255	532	656	84	927
33	876	468	295	680	482	280	681	472	297	674	483	284	676	488	285	670	489	290	664	476	301	666	493	291	659	478	305	660	86	929
31	875	673	491	279	658	492	293	675	485	283	662	487	294	663	481	299	668	475	300	679	477	287	669	470	304	683	471	289	87	931
935	92	302	657	484	303	671	469	296	661	486	298	672	473	292	677	474	286	678	479	288	665	490	281	682	480	282	667	494	870	27
937	94	306	430	707	320	415	708	310	432	701	321	419	703	326	420	697	327	425	691	314	436	693	331	426	686	316	440	687	868	25
939	96	700	329	414	685	330	428	702	323	418	689	325	429	690	319	434	695	313	435	706	315	422	696	308	439	710	309	424	866	23
941	98	437	684	322	438	698	307	431	688	324	433	699	311	427	704	312	421	705	317	423	692	328	416	709	318	417	694	332	864	21
943	100	360	727	356	374	712	357	364	729	350	375	716	352	380	717	346	381	722	340	368	733	342	385	723	335	370	737	336	862	19
945	102	349	383	711	334	384	725	351	377	715	338	379	726	339	373	731	344	367	732	355	369	719	345	362	736	359	363	721	860	17
947	104	734	333	376	735	347	361	728	337	378	730	348	365	724	353	366	718	354	371	720	341	382	713	358	372	714	343	386	858	15
949	106	171	457	815	185	442	816	175	459	809	186	446	811	191	447	805	192	452	799	179	463	801	196	453	794	181	467	795	856	13
951	108	808	194	441	793	195	455	810	188	445	797	190	456	798	184	461	803	178	462	814	180	449	804	173	466	818	174	451	854	11
953	110	464	792	187	465	806	172	458	796	189	460	807	176	454	812	177	448	813	182	450	800	193	443	817	183	444	802	197	852	9
955	112	198	835	410	212	820	411	202	837	404	213	824	406	218	825	400	219	830	394	206	841	396	223	831	389	208	845	390	850	7
957	114	403	221	819	388	222	833	405	215	823	392	217	834	393	211	839	398	205	840	409	207	827	399	200	844	413	201	829	848	5
959	116	842	387	214	843	401	199	836	391	216	838	402	203	832	407	204	826	408	209	828	395	220	821	412	210	822	397	224	846	3
961	90	901	899	897	895	893	891	889	887	885	883	881	879	877	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	874	1
32	60	58	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	933	934	936	938	940	942	944	946	948	950	952	954	956	958	960	30

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31, where the magic square of order 27 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{31 \times 31} := 14911, \quad S_{29 \times 29} := 13949, \quad S_{27 \times 27} := 12997 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{9 \times 9} := 4329.$$

Blocks of order 9 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**. Also the sum of 9 members of each block of order 3 are the same as of magic square of order 9.

2.11.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 729 by 169 to 793 in Example 3.23 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{25 \times 25}$ appearing in Example 2.11, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 given by

932	902	904	906	908	910	912	914	916	918	920	922	924	926	928	29	28	26	24	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	930
59	88	61	63	65	67	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	873	871	869	867	865	863	861	859	857	855	853	851	849	847	872	903
57	900	820	794	796	798	800	802	804	806	808	810	812	814	816	141	140	138	136	134	132	130	128	126	124	122	120	118	818	62	905
55	898	167	169	337	475	643	781	611	749	292	305	448	403	441	579	722	260	715	233	371	534	552	507	645	688	201	364	795	64	907
53	896	165	625	793	181	319	487	317	455	598	761	274	729	247	410	428	591	521	559	702	240	383	213	351	514	657	670	797	66	909
51	894	163	331	469	637	775	193	748	286	299	467	605	435	578	741	254	397	227	390	533	546	709	664	682	195	363	501	799	68	911
49	892	161	787	175	343	481	619	449	617	755	273	311	266	404	422	585	728	558	696	234	377	540	345	513	651	689	207	801	70	913
47	890	159	493	631	769	187	325	280	298	461	599	767	572	735	253	416	429	384	527	565	708	221	676	214	357	495	663	803	72	915
45	888	157	703	241	379	522	560	515	658	671	209	352	182	320	488	626	789	594	762	275	318	456	411	424	592	730	248	805	74	917
43	886	155	529	547	710	228	391	196	359	502	665	683	638	776	189	332	470	300	468	606	744	287	742	255	398	436	574	807	76	919
41	884	153	235	378	541	554	697	652	690	208	346	509	339	482	620	788	176	756	269	312	450	618	423	586	724	267	405	809	78	921
39	882	151	566	704	222	385	528	358	496	659	677	215	770	188	326	489	632	462	600	768	281	294	249	417	430	573	736	811	80	923
37	880	149	372	535	553	716	229	684	202	365	508	646	476	639	782	170	338	293	306	444	612	750	580	723	261	399	442	813	82	925
35	878	147	607	745	288	301	464	394	437	575	743	256	711	224	392	530	548	503	666	679	197	360	190	333	471	634	777	815	84	927
33	876	145	313	451	614	757	270	725	268	406	419	587	542	555	698	236	374	204	347	510	653	691	621	784	177	340	483	817	86	929
31	875	143	764	282	295	463	601	431	569	737	250	418	223	386	524	567	705	660	678	216	354	497	327	490	633	771	184	819	87	931
935	92	823	445	613	751	289	307	262	400	443	581	719	549	717	230	373	536	366	504	647	685	203	783	171	334	477	640	139	870	27
937	94	825	276	314	457	595	763	593	731	244	412	425	380	523	561	699	242	672	210	353	516	654	484	627	790	183	321	137	868	25
939	96	827	511	649	692	205	348	178	341	479	622	785	615	758	271	309	452	407	420	588	726	264	694	237	375	543	556	135	866	23
941	98	829	217	355	498	661	674	629	772	185	328	491	296	459	602	765	283	738	251	414	432	570	525	568	706	219	387	133	864	21
943	100	831	648	686	199	367	505	335	478	641	779	172	752	290	308	446	609	439	582	720	263	401	231	369	537	550	718	131	862	19
945	102	833	349	517	655	673	211	791	179	322	485	628	458	596	759	277	315	245	413	426	589	732	562	700	243	381	519	129	860	17
947	104	835	680	198	361	499	667	472	635	778	191	329	284	302	465	608	746	576	739	257	395	438	393	531	544	712	225	127	858	15
949	106	837	415	433	571	734	252	707	220	388	526	564	494	662	675	218	356	186	324	492	630	773	603	766	279	297	460	125	856	13
951	108	839	721	259	402	440	583	538	551	714	232	370	200	368	506	644	687	642	780	173	336	474	304	447	610	753	291	123	854	11
953	110	841	427	590	733	246	409	239	382	520	563	701	656	669	212	350	518	323	486	624	792	180	760	278	316	454	597	121	852	9
955	112	843	258	396	434	577	740	545	713	226	389	532	362	500	668	681	194	774	192	330	473	636	466	604	747	285	303	119	850	7
957	114	845	584	727	265	408	421	376	539	557	695	238	693	206	344	512	650	480	623	786	174	342	272	310	453	616	754	117	848	5
959	116	144	168	166	164	162	160	158	156	154	152	150	148	146	821	822	824	826	828	830	832	834	836	838	840	842	844	142	846	3
961	90	901	899	897	895	893	891	889	887	885	883	881	879	877	89	91	93	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	874	1
32	60	58	56	54	52	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	933	934	936	938	940	942	944	946	948	950	952	954	956	958	960	30

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 31, where the magic square of order 25 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** with following sums:

$$S_{31 \times 31} := 14911, \quad S_{29 \times 29} := 13949, \quad S_{27 \times 27} := 12997, \quad S_{25 \times 25} := 12025 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 2405.$$

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**. The magic square of order 25 is **bimagic square** with **bimagic sum**, $Sb_{25 \times 25} := 6597825$.

Summarizing, we have following result

Result 2.11. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 in two different ways. The blocks are considered as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 27, where blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 27, where blocks of order 9 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.*
- (iii) *Pandiagonal bimagic square of 25, where blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.*

The process applied here is the same as in case of magic square of order 29, but with different entries.

3 Appendix: Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares

This section brings the **block-wise** constructions of **magic** or **bimagic squares** of orders 8, 9, 12, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 24, 25 and 27. Most of these magic squares are author's construction. For more details refer [6, 8, 28, 29, 30, 31]. These magic squares are used in Section 2 in constructions of **block-bordered magic squares** of orders 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 19, 22, 23, 26, 29 and 31.

3.1 Magic Squares of Order 12

In this subsection, we shall present three different ways of writing block-wise magic square of order 12. One as 4×3 , i.e., magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. Second as 3×4 , i.e., magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

3.1.1 Second Approach: 12 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.1. 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 constructed using Example 1.1 and arranging according to Example 1.2 lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 given by

		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
	55	45	68	96	106	83	13	27	2	126	112	137	870
870	69	56	43	82	95	108	3	14	25	136	125	114	870
870	44	67	57	107	84	94	26	1	15	113	138	124	870
870	18	28	5	121	111	134	60	46	71	91	105	80	870
870	4	17	30	135	122	109	70	59	48	81	92	103	870
870	29	6	16	110	133	123	47	72	58	104	79	93	870
870	132	118	143	19	33	8	90	100	77	49	39	62	870
870	142	131	120	9	20	31	76	89	102	63	50	37	870
870	119	144	130	32	7	21	101	78	88	38	61	51	870
870	85	99	74	54	40	65	127	117	140	24	34	11	870
870	75	86	97	64	53	42	141	128	115	10	23	36	870
870	98	73	87	41	66	52	116	139	129	35	12	22	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

We observe that it is not possible to have equal magic sums of order 3 as it is impossible to divide magic sum of order 12 by 4, i.e., $870/4=217.5$. In this case, all the 3×3 blocks are magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums giving again a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given in example below.

Example 3.2. The magic sums of 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 appearing in Example 3.3 given above lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given by

		870	870	870	870
	168	285	42	375	870
870	51	366	177	276	870
870	393	60	267	150	870
870	258	159	384	69	870
	870	870	870	870	870

3.1.2 First Approach: 9 Blocks of Order 4

Example 3.3. 9 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4 constructed using Example 1.2 lead us to a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 12 given by

		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
	55	108	1	126	56	107	2	125	57	106	3	124	870
870	18	109	72	91	17	110	71	92	16	111	70	93	870
870	144	19	90	37	143	20	89	38	142	21	88	39	870
870	73	54	127	36	74	53	128	35	75	52	129	34	870
870	58	105	4	123	59	104	5	122	60	103	6	121	870
870	15	112	69	94	14	113	68	95	13	114	67	96	870
870	141	22	87	40	140	23	86	41	139	24	85	42	870
870	76	51	130	33	77	50	131	32	78	49	132	31	870
870	61	102	7	120	62	101	8	119	63	100	9	118	870
870	12	115	66	97	11	116	65	98	10	117	64	99	870
870	138	25	84	43	137	26	83	44	136	27	82	45	870
870	79	48	133	30	80	47	134	29	81	46	135	28	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{12 \times 12} = 870$. All the 4×4 blocks are **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 290$.

3.1.3 Third Approach: 4 Blocks of Order 6

Example 3.4. 4 blocks of magic squares of order 6 constructed using Example 1.4 lead us to a magic square of order 12 given by

												870
1	137	136	129	8	24	2	138	135	130	7	23	870
120	32	112	33	41	97	119	31	111	34	42	98	870
96	89	57	64	80	49	95	90	58	63	79	50	870
72	56	81	88	65	73	71	55	82	87	66	74	870
25	104	40	105	113	48	26	103	39	106	114	47	870
121	17	9	16	128	144	122	18	10	15	127	143	870
3	139	134	131	6	22	4	140	133	132	5	21	870
118	30	110	35	43	99	117	29	109	36	44	100	870
94	91	59	62	78	51	93	92	60	61	77	52	870
70	54	83	86	67	75	69	53	84	85	68	76	870
27	102	38	107	115	46	28	101	37	108	116	45	870
123	19	11	14	126	142	124	20	12	13	125	141	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{12 \times 12} := 870$, and all the four blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums $S_{6 \times 6} := 435$.

3.2 Magic Squares of Order 15

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of writing block-wise magic square of order 15. One as 5×3 , i.e., magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums. The second as 3×5 , i.e., magic square formed by 25 blocks semi-magic squares of order 3 (only in rows and columns) with equal semi-magic sums.

3.2.1 First Approach: 25 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.5. 25 blocks of order 3 constructed according to Example 1.1 lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 given by

		1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695
	186	65	88	187	74	78	188	75	76	189	64	86	190	62	87	1695
1695	80	193	66	89	183	67	90	181	68	79	191	69	77	192	70	1695
1695	73	81	185	63	82	194	61	83	195	71	84	184	72	85	182	1695
1695	36	200	103	37	209	93	38	210	91	39	199	101	40	197	102	1695
1695	95	43	201	104	33	202	105	31	203	94	41	204	92	42	205	1695
1695	208	96	35	198	97	44	196	98	45	206	99	34	207	100	32	1695
1695	6	215	118	7	224	108	8	225	106	9	214	116	10	212	117	1695
1695	110	13	216	119	3	217	120	1	218	109	11	219	107	12	220	1695
1695	223	111	5	213	112	14	211	113	15	221	114	4	222	115	2	1695
1695	156	50	133	157	59	123	158	60	121	159	49	131	160	47	132	1695
1695	125	163	51	134	153	52	135	151	53	124	161	54	122	162	55	1695
1695	58	126	155	48	127	164	46	128	165	56	129	154	57	130	152	1695
1695	171	20	148	172	29	138	173	30	136	174	19	146	175	17	147	1695
1695	140	178	21	149	168	22	150	166	23	139	176	24	137	177	25	1695
1695	28	141	170	18	142	179	16	143	180	26	144	169	27	145	167	1695
	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{15 \times 15} = 1695$. All the 3×3 blocks are **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with equal **semi-magic** sums, i.e., $S_{3 \times 3} = 339$ (in rows and columns).

3.2.2 Second Approach: 9 Blocks of Order 5

Example 3.6. 9 *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5 constructed according to Example 1.3 lead us to a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 15 given by

		1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695
	1	87	111	178	188	3	86	110	179	187	2	85	109	180	189	1695
1695	171	193	8	76	117	170	194	7	78	116	169	195	9	77	115	1695
1695	83	106	177	186	13	82	108	176	185	14	84	107	175	184	15	1695
1695	192	6	88	113	166	191	5	89	112	168	190	4	90	114	167	1695
1695	118	173	181	12	81	119	172	183	11	80	120	174	182	10	79	1695
1695	31	72	96	163	203	33	71	95	164	202	32	70	94	165	204	1695
1695	156	208	38	61	102	155	209	37	63	101	154	210	39	62	100	1695
1695	68	91	162	201	43	67	93	161	200	44	69	92	160	199	45	1695
1695	207	36	73	98	151	206	35	74	97	153	205	34	75	99	152	1695
1695	103	158	196	42	66	104	157	198	41	65	105	159	197	40	64	1695
1695	16	57	126	148	218	18	56	125	149	217	17	55	124	150	219	1695
1695	141	223	23	46	132	140	224	22	48	131	139	225	24	47	130	1695
1695	53	121	147	216	28	52	123	146	215	29	54	122	145	214	30	1695
1695	222	21	58	128	136	221	20	59	127	138	220	19	60	129	137	1695
1695	133	143	211	27	51	134	142	213	26	50	135	144	212	25	49	1695
	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{15 \times 15} = 1695$. All the 5×5 blocks are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums $S_{5 \times 5} = 565$.

3.3 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 16

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of writing magic squares of order 16. One is **pandiagonal** magic square formed by 16 **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 of equal magic sums. The second is **bimagic** square of order 16.

3.3.1 First Approach: Pan Magic Square of Order 16

Example 3.7. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 constructed according to Example 1.2 is given by

		2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056
	97	192	1	224	98	191	2	223	99	190	3	222	100	189	4	221	2056	
2056	32	193	128	161	31	194	127	162	30	195	126	163	29	196	125	164	2056	
2056	256	33	160	65	255	34	159	66	254	35	158	67	253	36	157	68	2056	
2056	129	96	225	64	130	95	226	63	131	94	227	62	132	93	228	61	2056	
2056	101	188	5	220	102	187	6	219	103	186	7	218	104	185	8	217	2056	
2056	28	197	124	165	27	198	123	166	26	199	122	167	25	200	121	168	2056	
2056	252	37	156	69	251	38	155	70	250	39	154	71	249	40	153	72	2056	
2056	133	92	229	60	134	91	230	59	135	90	231	58	136	89	232	57	2056	
2056	105	184	9	216	106	183	10	215	107	182	11	214	108	181	12	213	2056	
2056	24	201	120	169	23	202	119	170	22	203	118	171	21	204	117	172	2056	
2056	248	41	152	73	247	42	151	74	246	43	150	75	245	44	149	76	2056	
2056	137	88	233	56	138	87	234	55	139	86	235	54	140	85	236	53	2056	
2056	109	180	13	212	110	179	14	211	111	178	15	210	112	177	16	209	2056	
2056	20	205	116	173	19	206	115	174	18	207	114	175	17	208	113	176	2056	
2056	244	45	148	77	243	46	147	78	242	47	146	79	241	48	145	80	2056	
2056	141	84	237	52	142	83	238	51	143	82	239	50	144	81	240	49	2056	
	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{16 \times 16} = 2056$. All the 4×4 blocks are **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 514$.

3.3.2 Second Approach: Bimagic Square of Order 16

Example 3.8. A *bimagic* square of order 16 is given by

																2056
1	154	239	120	23	144	249	98	44	179	198	93	62	165	212	75	2056
232	127	10	145	242	105	32	135	205	86	35	188	219	68	53	174	2056
122	225	152	15	112	247	130	25	83	204	189	38	69	222	171	52	2056
159	8	113	234	137	18	103	256	182	45	92	195	164	59	78	213	2056
46	181	196	91	60	163	214	77	7	160	233	114	17	138	255	104	2056
203	84	37	190	221	70	51	172	226	121	16	151	248	111	26	129	2056
85	206	187	36	67	220	173	54	128	231	146	9	106	241	136	31	2056
180	43	94	197	166	61	76	211	153	2	119	240	143	24	97	250	2056
55	176	217	66	33	186	207	88	30	133	244	107	12	147	230	125	2056
210	73	64	167	200	95	42	177	251	100	21	142	237	118	3	156	2056
80	215	162	57	90	193	184	47	101	254	139	20	115	236	157	6	2056
169	50	71	224	191	40	81	202	132	27	110	245	150	13	124	227	2056
28	131	246	109	14	149	228	123	49	170	223	72	39	192	201	82	2056
253	102	19	140	235	116	5	158	216	79	58	161	194	89	48	183	2056
99	252	141	22	117	238	155	4	74	209	168	63	96	199	178	41	2056
134	29	108	243	148	11	126	229	175	56	65	218	185	34	87	208	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

3.4 Magic Square of Order 18

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of writing magic square of order 18. One is with 36 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. The second is with 9 blocks of magic squares of order 6 of equal magic sums.

3.4.1 First Approach: 36 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.9. *By the applications of Examples 1.1 and 1.4, we get a magic square of order 18 given by*

																		2925
19	39	2	193	177	212	246	262	227	300	280	317	139	159	122	78	58	95	2925
3	20	37	213	194	175	226	245	264	316	299	282	123	140	157	94	77	60	2925
38	1	21	176	211	195	263	228	244	281	318	298	158	121	141	59	96	76	2925
247	267	230	73	57	92	301	285	320	132	148	113	187	171	206	31	51	14	2925
231	248	265	93	74	55	321	302	283	112	131	150	207	188	169	15	32	49	2925
266	229	249	56	91	75	284	319	303	149	114	130	170	205	189	50	13	33	2925
90	70	107	36	52	17	127	147	110	241	261	224	289	273	308	192	172	209	2925
106	89	72	16	35	54	111	128	145	225	242	259	309	290	271	208	191	174	2925
71	108	88	53	18	34	146	109	129	260	223	243	272	307	291	173	210	190	2925
294	274	311	138	154	119	30	46	11	198	178	215	84	64	101	235	255	218	2925
310	293	276	118	137	156	10	29	48	214	197	180	100	83	66	219	236	253	2925
275	312	292	155	120	136	47	12	28	179	216	196	65	102	82	254	217	237	2925
181	165	200	295	279	314	85	69	104	25	45	8	252	268	233	133	153	116	2925
201	182	163	315	296	277	105	86	67	9	26	43	232	251	270	117	134	151	2925
164	199	183	278	313	297	68	103	87	44	7	27	269	234	250	152	115	135	2925
144	160	125	240	256	221	186	166	203	79	63	98	24	40	5	306	286	323	2925
124	143	162	220	239	258	202	185	168	99	80	61	4	23	42	322	305	288	2925
161	126	142	257	222	238	167	204	184	62	97	81	41	6	22	287	324	304	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

We observe that it is not possible to have equal magic sums of order 3 as it is impossible to divide magic sum of order 18 by 6, i.e., $2925/6=487.5$. All the 36 blocks are magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums resulting again a magic square of order 6 given in example below.

Example 3.10. *The magic sums of magic squares of order 3 of Example 3.9 lead us to magic square of order 6 given by*

						2925
60	582	735	897	420	231	2925
744	222	906	393	564	96	2925
267	105	384	726	870	573	2925
879	411	87	591	249	708	2925
546	888	258	78	753	402	2925
429	717	555	240	69	915	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

3.4.2 Second Approach: 9 Blocks of Order 6

Example 3.11. *9 blocks of magic squares of order 6 constructed according to Example 1.4 lead us to a magic square of order 18 given by*

																		2925
1	307	306	289	18	54	2	308	305	290	17	53	3	309	304	291	16	52	2925
270	72	252	73	91	217	269	71	251	74	92	218	268	70	250	75	93	219	2925
216	199	127	144	180	109	215	200	128	143	179	110	214	201	129	142	178	111	2925
162	126	181	198	145	163	161	125	182	197	146	164	160	124	183	196	147	165	2925
55	234	90	235	253	108	56	233	89	236	254	107	57	232	88	237	255	106	2925
271	37	19	36	288	324	272	38	20	35	287	323	273	39	21	34	286	322	2925
4	310	303	292	15	51	5	311	302	293	14	50	6	312	301	294	13	49	2925
267	69	249	76	94	220	266	68	248	77	95	221	265	67	247	78	96	222	2925
213	202	130	141	177	112	212	203	131	140	176	113	211	204	132	139	175	114	2925
159	123	184	195	148	166	158	122	185	194	149	167	157	121	186	193	150	168	2925
58	231	87	238	256	105	59	230	86	239	257	104	60	229	85	240	258	103	2925
274	40	22	33	285	321	275	41	23	32	284	320	276	42	24	31	283	319	2925
7	313	300	295	12	48	8	314	299	296	11	47	9	315	298	297	10	46	2925
264	66	246	79	97	223	263	65	245	80	98	224	262	64	244	81	99	225	2925
210	205	133	138	174	115	209	206	134	137	173	116	208	207	135	136	172	117	2925
156	120	187	192	151	169	155	119	188	191	152	170	154	118	189	190	153	171	2925
61	228	84	241	259	102	62	227	83	242	260	101	63	226	82	243	261	100	2925
277	43	25	30	282	318	278	44	26	29	281	317	279	45	27	28	280	316	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

The above magic square is with magic sum $S_{18 \times 18} = 2925$, and all the 9 blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} := 975$.

3.5 Magic Square of Order 20

In this subsection, we shall present three different ways of writing block-wise magic square of order 20. One as 4×5 , i.e., magic square formed by 25 blocks of equal magic sums of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The second as 5×4 , i.e., magic square formed by 16 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums. The third as 4 blocks of equal magic sums of magic squares of order 10. In the first two cases, the magic squares are **pandiagonals**, while in the third case is just a magic square of order 20.

3.5.1 First Approach: 25 Blocks of Order 4

Example 3.12. 25 blocks of magic squares of order 4 constructed according to Example 1.2 lead us to a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 20 is given by

		4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010
	151	300	1	350	152	299	2	349	153	298	3	348	154	297	4	347	155	296	5	346	4010
4010	50	301	200	251	49	302	199	252	48	303	198	253	47	304	197	254	46	305	196	255	4010
4010	400	51	250	101	399	52	249	102	398	53	248	103	397	54	247	104	396	55	246	105	4010
4010	201	150	351	100	202	149	352	99	203	148	353	98	204	147	354	97	205	146	355	96	4010
4010	156	295	6	345	157	294	7	344	158	293	8	343	159	292	9	342	160	291	10	341	4010
4010	45	306	195	256	44	307	194	257	43	308	193	258	42	309	192	259	41	310	191	260	4010
4010	395	56	245	106	394	57	244	107	393	58	243	108	392	59	242	109	391	60	241	110	4010
4010	206	145	356	95	207	144	357	94	208	143	358	93	209	142	359	92	210	141	360	91	4010
4010	161	290	11	340	162	289	12	339	163	288	13	338	164	287	14	337	165	286	15	336	4010
4010	40	311	190	261	39	312	189	262	38	313	188	263	37	314	187	264	36	315	186	265	4010
4010	390	61	240	111	389	62	239	112	388	63	238	113	387	64	237	114	386	65	236	115	4010
4010	211	140	361	90	212	139	362	89	213	138	363	88	214	137	364	87	215	136	365	86	4010
4010	166	285	16	335	167	284	17	334	168	283	18	333	169	282	19	332	170	281	20	331	4010
4010	35	316	185	266	34	317	184	267	33	318	183	268	32	319	182	269	31	320	181	270	4010
4010	385	66	235	116	384	67	234	117	383	68	233	118	382	69	232	119	381	70	231	120	4010
4010	216	135	366	85	217	134	367	84	218	133	368	83	219	132	369	82	220	131	370	81	4010
4010	171	280	21	330	172	279	22	329	173	278	23	328	174	277	24	327	175	276	25	326	4010
4010	30	321	180	271	29	322	179	272	28	323	178	273	27	324	177	274	26	325	176	275	4010
4010	380	71	230	121	379	72	229	122	378	73	228	123	377	74	227	124	376	75	226	125	4010
4010	221	130	371	80	222	129	372	79	223	128	373	78	224	127	374	77	225	126	375	76	4010
	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{20 \times 20} = 4010$. All the 4×4 blocks are **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 with the equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 802$.

3.5.2 Second Approach: 16 Blocks of Order 5

Example 3.13. 16 blocks of magic squares of order 5 constructed according to Example 1.3 lead us to a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 20 given by

3.5.3 Third Approach: 4 Blocks of Order 10

Example 3.15. *4 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 10 constructed according to Example ?? lead us to a magic square of order 20 given by*

																				4010	
1	177	72	384	336	88	309	153	240	245	2	178	71	383	335	87	310	154	239	246	4010	
152	64	256	325	100	397	161	228	9	313	151	63	255	326	99	398	162	227	10	314	4010	
244	236	85	180	392	13	157	321	308	69	243	235	86	179	391	14	158	322	307	70	4010	
80	333	229	148	301	165	396	4	252	97	79	334	230	147	302	166	395	3	251	98	4010	
388	81	17	233	169	304	332	260	65	156	387	82	18	234	170	303	331	259	66	155	4010	
329	248	141	317	73	232	20	385	96	164	330	247	142	318	74	231	19	386	95	163	4010	
176	5	320	92	224	149	253	77	381	328	175	6	319	91	223	150	254	78	382	327	4010	
93	389	168	61	257	340	225	316	144	12	94	390	167	62	258	339	226	315	143	11	4010	
305	160	393	249	8	76	84	172	337	221	306	159	394	250	7	75	83	171	338	222	4010	
237	312	324	16	145	241	68	89	173	400	238	311	323	15	146	242	67	90	174	399	4010	
21	197	52	364	356	108	289	133	220	265	22	198	51	363	355	107	290	134	219	266	4010	
132	44	276	345	120	377	181	208	29	293	131	43	275	346	119	378	182	207	30	294	4010	
264	216	105	200	372	33	137	341	288	49	263	215	106	199	371	34	138	342	287	50	4010	
60	353	209	128	281	185	376	24	272	117	59	354	210	127	282	186	375	23	271	118	4010	
368	101	37	213	189	284	352	280	45	136	367	102	38	214	190	283	351	279	46	135	4010	
349	268	121	297	53	212	40	365	116	184	350	267	122	298	54	211	39	366	115	183	4010	
196	25	300	112	204	129	273	57	361	348	195	26	299	111	203	130	274	58	362	347	4010	
113	369	188	41	277	360	205	296	124	32	114	370	187	42	278	359	206	295	123	31	4010	
285	140	373	269	28	56	104	192	357	201	286	139	374	270	27	55	103	191	358	202	4010	
217	292	344	36	125	261	48	109	193	380	218	291	343	35	126	262	47	110	194	379	4010	
4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010

The above magic square is with magic sum $S_{20 \times 20} = 4010$, and all the four blocks of order 10 are magic squares with equal magic sums $S_{10 \times 10} := 2005$.

3.6 Magic Square of Order 21

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of writing block-wise **pandiagonal** magic square of order 21. One as 7×3 , i.e., magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7. Second as 3×7 , i.e., magic square formed by 49 blocks semi-magic squares of order 3 with equal semi-magic sums (only in rows and columns). In both the cases the magic squares are **pandiagonal**

3.6.1 First Approach: 49 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.16. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 21 formed by 49 blocks of semi-magic squares of order 3 constructed according to Examples 1.1 and 1.5 is given by

		4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641
	246	111	306	232	123	308	250	110	303	233	125	305	252	109	302	234	122	307	247	112	304	4641
4641	300	243	120	312	245	106	299	240	124	314	242	107	298	239	126	311	244	108	301	241	121	4641
4641	117	309	237	119	295	249	114	313	236	116	296	251	113	315	235	118	297	248	115	310	238	4641
4641	288	363	12	274	375	14	292	362	9	275	377	11	294	361	8	276	374	13	289	364	10	4641
4641	6	285	372	18	287	358	5	282	376	20	284	359	4	281	378	17	286	360	7	283	373	4641
4641	369	15	279	371	1	291	366	19	278	368	2	293	365	21	277	370	3	290	367	16	280	4641
4641	183	90	390	169	102	392	187	89	387	170	104	389	189	88	386	171	101	391	184	91	388	4641
4641	384	180	99	396	182	85	383	177	103	398	179	86	382	176	105	395	181	87	385	178	100	4641
4641	96	393	174	98	379	186	93	397	173	95	380	188	92	399	172	97	381	185	94	394	175	4641
4641	225	405	33	211	417	35	229	404	30	212	419	32	231	403	29	213	416	34	226	406	31	4641
4641	27	222	414	39	224	400	26	219	418	41	221	401	25	218	420	38	223	402	28	220	415	4641
4641	411	36	216	413	22	228	408	40	215	410	23	230	407	42	214	412	24	227	409	37	217	4641
4641	162	69	432	148	81	434	166	68	429	149	83	431	168	67	428	150	80	433	163	70	430	4641
4641	426	159	78	438	161	64	425	156	82	440	158	65	424	155	84	437	160	66	427	157	79	4641
4641	75	435	153	77	421	165	72	439	152	74	422	167	71	441	151	76	423	164	73	436	154	4641
4641	267	342	54	253	354	56	271	341	51	254	356	53	273	340	50	255	353	55	268	343	52	4641
4641	48	264	351	60	266	337	47	261	355	62	263	338	46	260	357	59	265	339	49	262	352	4641
4641	348	57	258	350	43	270	345	61	257	347	44	272	344	63	256	349	45	269	346	58	259	4641
4641	204	132	327	190	144	329	208	131	324	191	146	326	210	130	323	192	143	328	205	133	325	4641
4641	321	201	141	333	203	127	320	198	145	335	200	128	319	197	147	332	202	129	322	199	142	4641
4641	138	330	195	140	316	207	135	334	194	137	317	209	134	336	193	139	318	206	136	331	196	4641
	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641	4641

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{21 \times 21} = 4641$. All the 3×3 blocks are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums, $S_{3 \times 3} = 663$ (in rows and columns).

3.6.2 Second Approach: 9 Blocks of Order 7

Example 3.17. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 21 formed by 9 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 7 constructed according to Example 1.5 is given by

3.7.1 First Approach: 64 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.18. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 24 formed by 64 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 3 constructed according to Examples 1.1 and 1.6 is given by

		6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924
	253	231	278	336	358	311	25	51	2	540	514	563	258	232	281	331	357	308	30	52	5	535	513	560	6924
6924	279	254	229	310	335	360	3	26	49	562	539	516	280	257	234	309	332	355	4	29	54	561	536	511	6924
6924	230	277	255	359	312	334	50	1	27	515	564	538	233	282	256	356	307	333	53	6	28	512	559	537	6924
6924	36	58	11	529	507	554	264	238	287	325	351	302	31	57	8	534	508	557	259	237	284	330	352	305	6924
6924	10	35	60	555	530	505	286	263	240	303	326	349	9	32	55	556	533	510	285	260	235	304	329	354	6924
6924	59	12	34	506	553	531	239	288	262	350	301	327	56	7	33	509	558	532	236	283	261	353	306	328	6924
6924	552	526	575	37	63	14	324	346	299	241	219	266	547	525	572	42	64	17	319	345	296	246	220	269	6924
6924	574	551	528	15	38	61	298	323	348	267	242	217	573	548	523	16	41	66	297	320	343	268	245	222	6924
6924	527	576	550	62	13	39	347	300	322	218	265	243	524	571	549	65	18	40	344	295	321	221	270	244	6924
6924	313	339	290	252	226	275	541	519	566	48	70	23	318	340	293	247	225	272	546	520	569	43	69	20	6924
6924	291	314	337	274	251	228	567	542	517	22	47	72	292	317	342	273	248	223	568	545	522	21	44	67	6924
6924	338	289	315	227	276	250	518	565	543	71	24	46	341	294	316	224	271	249	521	570	544	68	19	45	6924
6924	181	207	158	408	382	431	97	75	122	468	490	443	186	208	161	403	381	428	102	76	125	463	489	440	6924
6924	159	182	205	430	407	384	123	98	73	442	467	492	160	185	210	429	404	379	124	101	78	441	464	487	6924
6924	206	157	183	383	432	406	74	121	99	491	444	466	209	162	184	380	427	405	77	126	100	488	439	465	6924
6924	108	82	131	457	483	434	192	214	167	397	375	422	103	81	128	462	484	437	187	213	164	402	376	425	6924
6924	130	107	84	435	458	481	166	191	216	423	398	373	129	104	79	436	461	486	165	188	211	424	401	378	6924
6924	83	132	106	482	433	459	215	168	190	374	421	399	80	127	105	485	438	460	212	163	189	377	426	400	6924
6924	480	502	455	109	87	134	396	370	419	169	195	146	475	501	452	114	88	137	391	369	416	174	196	149	6924
6924	454	479	504	135	110	85	418	395	372	147	170	193	453	476	499	136	113	90	417	392	367	148	173	198	6924
6924	503	456	478	86	133	111	371	420	394	194	145	171	500	451	477	89	138	112	368	415	393	197	150	172	6924
6924	385	363	410	180	202	155	469	495	446	120	94	143	390	364	413	175	201	152	474	496	449	115	93	140	6924
6924	411	386	361	154	179	204	447	470	493	142	119	96	412	389	366	153	176	199	448	473	498	141	116	91	6924
6924	362	409	387	203	156	178	494	445	471	95	144	118	365	414	388	200	151	177	497	450	472	92	139	117	6924
	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924

We observe that it is not possible to have equal magic sums of order 3 as it is impossible to divide magic sum of order 24 by 8, i.e., $6924/8:=865.5$. In this case, Blocks of 3×3 are magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums resulting in a **pandiagonal semi-bimagic square** of order 24 with **semi-bimagic sum** $S_{24 \times 24} := 2661124$. Also, the sums of magic squares of order 3 results in a **pandiagonal magic square** of order 8 given in example below:

Example 3.19. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 arising due to magic sums of order 3 of Exemple 3.20 is given by

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{24 \times 24} := 6924$. All the 36 blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} := 1154$.

3.7.3 Third Approach: 16 Blocks of Order 6

Example 3.21. A magic square of order 24 formed by 16 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 6 is given by

																								6924
1	545	544	513	32	96	2	546	543	514	31	95	3	547	542	515	30	94	4	548	541	516	29	93	6924
480	128	448	129	161	385	479	127	447	130	162	386	478	126	446	131	163	387	477	125	445	132	164	388	6924
384	353	225	256	320	193	383	354	226	255	319	194	382	355	227	254	318	195	381	356	228	253	317	196	6924
288	224	321	352	257	289	287	223	322	351	258	290	286	222	323	350	259	291	285	221	324	349	260	292	6924
97	416	160	417	449	192	98	415	159	418	450	191	99	414	158	419	451	190	100	413	157	420	452	189	6924
481	65	33	64	512	576	482	66	34	63	511	575	483	67	35	62	510	574	484	68	36	61	509	573	6924
5	549	540	517	28	92	6	550	539	518	27	91	7	551	538	519	26	90	8	552	537	520	25	89	6924
476	124	444	133	165	389	475	123	443	134	166	390	474	122	442	135	167	391	473	121	441	136	168	392	6924
380	357	229	252	316	197	379	358	230	251	315	198	378	359	231	250	314	199	377	360	232	249	313	200	6924
284	220	325	348	261	293	283	219	326	347	262	294	282	218	327	346	263	295	281	217	328	345	264	296	6924
101	412	156	421	453	188	102	411	155	422	454	187	103	410	154	423	455	186	104	409	153	424	456	185	6924
485	69	37	60	508	572	486	70	38	59	507	571	487	71	39	58	506	570	488	72	40	57	505	569	6924
9	553	536	521	24	88	10	554	535	522	23	87	11	555	534	523	22	86	12	556	533	524	21	85	6924
472	120	440	137	169	393	471	119	439	138	170	394	470	118	438	139	171	395	469	117	437	140	172	396	6924
376	361	233	248	312	201	375	362	234	247	311	202	374	363	235	246	310	203	373	364	236	245	309	204	6924
280	216	329	344	265	297	279	215	330	343	266	298	278	214	331	342	267	299	277	213	332	341	268	300	6924
105	408	152	425	457	184	106	407	151	426	458	183	107	406	150	427	459	182	108	405	149	428	460	181	6924
489	73	41	56	504	568	490	74	42	55	503	567	491	75	43	54	502	566	492	76	44	53	501	565	6924
13	557	532	525	20	84	14	558	531	526	19	83	15	559	530	527	18	82	16	560	529	528	17	81	6924
468	116	436	141	173	397	467	115	435	142	174	398	466	114	434	143	175	399	465	113	433	144	176	400	6924
372	365	237	244	308	205	371	366	238	243	307	206	370	367	239	242	306	207	369	368	240	241	305	208	6924
276	212	333	340	269	301	275	211	334	339	270	302	274	210	335	338	271	303	273	209	336	337	272	304	6924
109	404	148	429	461	180	110	403	147	430	462	179	111	402	146	431	463	178	112	401	145	432	464	177	6924
493	77	45	52	500	564	494	78	46	51	499	563	495	79	47	50	498	562	496	80	48	49	497	561	6924
6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924

The above magic square is with magic sum $S_{24 \times 24} = 6924$, and all the 16 blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums $S_{6 \times 6} := 1731$.

3.7.4 Forth Approach: Semi-Bimagic Square of Order 24

Below is a magic square of order 24 with 9 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 8. The magic square is **semi-bimagic** square of order 24.

Example 3.22. A *semi-bimagic* square of order 24 formed by 9 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 8 constructed according to Examples 1.7 is given by

																								6924
142	411	298	15	273	568	453	148	119	386	323	38	248	545	476	173	96	361	348	61	223	522	499	198	6924
268	573	448	153	135	418	291	22	245	548	473	176	110	395	314	47	222	523	498	199	85	372	337	72	6924
3	310	423	130	160	441	556	285	26	335	398	107	185	464	533	260	49	360	373	84	210	487	510	235	6924
165	436	561	280	10	303	430	123	188	461	536	257	35	326	407	98	211	486	511	234	60	349	384	73	6924
304	9	124	429	435	166	279	562	329	32	101	404	458	191	254	539	354	55	78	379	481	216	229	516	6924
442	159	286	555	309	4	129	424	467	182	263	530	332	29	104	401	492	205	240	505	355	54	79	378	6924
417	136	21	292	574	267	154	447	392	113	44	317	551	242	179	470	367	90	67	342	528	217	204	493	6924
567	274	147	454	412	141	16	297	542	251	170	479	389	116	41	320	517	228	193	504	366	91	66	343	6924
95	362	347	62	224	521	500	197	144	409	300	13	271	570	451	150	118	387	322	39	249	544	477	172	6924
221	524	497	200	86	371	338	71	270	571	450	151	133	420	289	24	244	549	472	177	111	394	315	46	6924
50	359	374	83	209	488	509	236	1	312	421	132	162	439	558	283	27	334	399	106	184	465	532	261	6924
212	485	512	233	59	350	383	74	163	438	559	282	12	301	432	121	189	460	537	256	34	327	406	99	6924
353	56	77	380	482	215	230	515	306	7	126	427	433	168	277	564	328	33	100	405	459	190	255	538	6924
491	206	239	506	356	53	80	377	444	157	288	553	307	6	127	426	466	183	262	531	333	28	105	400	6924
368	89	68	341	527	218	203	494	415	138	19	294	576	265	156	445	393	112	45	316	550	243	178	471	6924
518	227	194	503	365	92	65	344	565	276	145	456	414	139	18	295	543	250	171	478	388	117	40	321	6924
120	385	324	37	247	546	475	174	94	363	346	63	225	520	501	196	143	410	299	14	272	569	452	149	6924
246	547	474	175	109	396	313	48	220	525	496	201	87	370	339	70	269	572	449	152	134	419	290	23	6924
25	336	397	108	186	463	534	259	51	358	375	82	208	489	508	237	2	311	422	131	161	440	557	284	6924
187	462	535	258	36	325	408	97	213	484	513	232	58	351	382	75	164	437	560	281	11	302	431	122	6924
330	31	102	403	457	192	253	540	352	57	76	381	483	214	231	514	305	8	125	428	434	167	278	563	6924
468	181	264	529	331	30	103	402	490	207	238	507	357	52	81	376	443	158	287	554	308	5	128	425	6924
391	114	43	318	552	241	180	469	369	88	69	340	526	219	202	495	416	137	20	293	575	266	155	446	6924
541	252	169	480	390	115	42	319	519	226	195	502	364	93	64	345	566	275	146	455	413	140	17	296	6924
6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924	6924

In this case, the magic square is formed by 9 blocks of magic squares of order 8 with equal magic sums $S_{8 \times 8} := 2308$. Out of 9 blocks of order 8, three of them are **bimagic** squares with different **bimagic** sums, and the other 6 are **semi-bimagic** (**bimagic** only in rows and columns) resulting in a **semi-bimagic** square of order 24 (**bimagic** only in rows and columns), with **semi-bimagic** sums are $Sb1_{24 \times 24} := 2661124$ (rows and columns), $Sb2_{24 \times 24} := 2654292$ (upper diagonal) and $Sb3_{24 \times 24} := 2714116$ (lower diagonal).

3.8 Bimagic Square of Order 25

In this subsection, we shall present a block-wise **pandiagonal** magic square of order 25 with 25 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The magic square is also **bimagic**.

Example 3.23. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 25 formed by 25 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5 constructed according to Example 1.3 is given by

		7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	
	1	220	284	498	562	417	606	75	139	328	183	272	461	530	119	599	38	227	316	385	365	429	518	82	171	7825
7825	484	573	12	201	295	150	339	403	617	56	536	105	194	258	472	302	391	585	49	238	93	157	371	440	504	7825
7825	212	276	495	559	23	603	67	131	350	414	269	458	547	111	180	35	249	313	377	591	446	515	79	168	357	7825
7825	570	9	223	287	476	331	425	614	53	142	122	186	255	469	533	388	577	41	235	324	154	368	432	521	90	7825
7825	298	487	551	20	209	64	128	342	406	625	455	544	108	197	261	241	310	399	588	27	507	96	165	354	443	7825
7825	583	47	236	305	394	374	438	502	91	160	15	204	293	482	571	401	620	59	148	337	192	256	475	539	103	7825
7825	311	380	594	33	247	77	166	360	449	513	493	557	21	215	279	134	348	412	601	70	550	114	178	267	456	7825
7825	44	233	322	386	580	435	524	88	152	366	221	290	479	568	7	612	51	145	334	423	253	467	531	125	189	7825
7825	397	586	30	244	308	163	352	441	510	99	554	18	207	296	490	345	409	623	62	126	106	200	264	453	542	7825
7825	230	319	383	597	36	516	85	174	363	427	282	496	565	4	218	73	137	326	420	609	464	528	117	181	275	7825
7825	415	604	68	132	346	176	270	459	548	112	592	31	250	314	378	358	447	511	80	169	24	213	277	491	560	7825
7825	143	332	421	615	54	534	123	187	251	470	325	389	578	42	231	86	155	369	433	522	477	566	10	224	288	7825
7825	621	65	129	343	407	262	451	545	109	198	28	242	306	400	589	444	508	97	161	355	210	299	488	552	16	7825
7825	329	418	607	71	140	120	184	273	462	526	381	600	39	228	317	172	361	430	519	83	563	2	216	285	499	7825
7825	57	146	340	404	618	473	537	101	195	259	239	303	392	581	50	505	94	158	372	436	291	485	574	13	202	7825
7825	367	431	525	89	153	8	222	286	480	569	424	613	52	141	335	190	254	468	532	121	576	45	234	323	387	7825
7825	100	164	353	442	506	486	555	19	208	297	127	341	410	624	63	543	107	196	265	454	309	398	587	26	245	7825
7825	428	517	81	175	364	219	283	497	561	5	610	74	138	327	416	271	465	529	118	182	37	226	320	384	598	7825
7825	156	375	439	503	92	572	11	205	294	483	338	402	616	60	149	104	193	257	471	540	395	584	48	237	301	7825
7825	514	78	167	356	450	280	494	558	22	211	66	135	349	413	602	457	546	115	179	268	248	312	376	595	34	7825
7825	199	263	452	541	110	590	29	243	307	396	351	445	509	98	162	17	206	300	489	553	408	622	61	130	344	7825
7825	527	116	185	274	463	318	382	596	40	229	84	173	362	426	520	500	564	3	217	281	136	330	419	608	72	7825
7825	260	474	538	102	191	46	240	304	393	582	437	501	95	159	373	203	292	481	575	14	619	58	147	336	405	7825
7825	113	177	266	460	549	379	593	32	246	315	170	359	448	512	76	556	25	214	278	492	347	411	605	69	133	7825
7825	466	535	124	188	252	232	321	390	579	43	523	87	151	370	434	289	478	567	6	225	55	144	333	422	611	7825
	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

In this case the **pandiagonal** magic square is **bimagic** with magic and **bimagic** sums, $S_{25 \times 25} := 7825$ and $Sb_{25 \times 25} := 3263025$ respectively. Each block of order 5 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with equal magic sums, $S_{5 \times 5} := 1565$. Details of this **bimagic** square can be seen in author's work [24].

3.9 Magic Squares of Order 27

In this subsection, we shall present three different ways of writing block-wise **pandiagonal** magic square of order 27. One as 3×9 , i.e., magic square formed by 81 blocks of equal sums semi-magic squares of order 3. Second as 9×3 , i.e., magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 9. Third as, 9 blocks of bimagic squares of order 9 resulting a magic square of order 27.

5. *Multi-digits and Number Patterns Magic Squares* - [25, 35];
6. *Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares with Uniformity, Minimum Sum and Pythagorean Triples* - [26, 27];
7. *Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares* - [19, 28, 29, 30, 31, 34, 37, 39];
8. *Magic Crosses: Repeated and Non Repeated Entries* - [32];
9. *Representations of Letters and Numbers With Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 6* - [33];
10. *Bordered Magic Squares* - [40, 41, 42, 43, 44];
11. *2-Digits Magic and Bimagic Squares* - [45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52].

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